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**ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION AND KNOWLEDGE
MANAGEMENT IN A SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN MALANG INDONESIA:
A CASE STUDY OF A LEARNING ORGANIZATION**

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31 May 2024

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This paper prepared by **TEGUH SANTOSO** with the title: “**ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION AND KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT IN A SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN MALANG INDONESIA: A CASE STUDY OF A LEARNING ORGANIZATION**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Communication.

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Biographical Sketch

Before joining the Doctoral program at UPOU and working as a lecturer, I graduated with a Master of Management from Gadjah Mada University, Yogyakarta, major in Strategic Management and International Business (obtained from De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines under a Student Exchange Program). Here, I was granted the Sampoerna Foundation Scholarship to take an Intensive International Class in the Master of Management with English as the medium of instruction. Before that, I was involved in management system audits in different organizations (as a freelancer certified auditor), such as Sono Kembang Catering Surabaya, BATAM Center on ISO 27001, PT Duta Bangsa Mandiri-manufacturing, etc. and also some Catholic School and its foundations in Malang, Surabaya, Bandung, Jakarta, and Palembang.

Based on these experiences, I believe that joining this doctoral communication program at UPOU is the best way to enhance my knowledge and skills. The opportunity to network with students, staff, and reputable lecturers--our mentors and partners in this journey are truly amazing!

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The author hopes that this thesis will enrich his and other scholars' insights. The author remains open to suggestions and feedback to improve this work. In particular, the author would like to thank the following people:

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Greg

Dedication

“If you can change your mind, you can change your life.” — William James

I dedicate this dissertation primarily to my family, especially my wife, parents, and aunt, who have been so supportive throughout the hassles of compiling and completing this dissertation. Likewise, I dedicate this work to Prof. Alexander Flor as the primary supervisor whose full of love and dedication, devoted all his thoughts and attention to the process of supervising the preparation of this dissertation, of course, accompanied by all the support from Prof. Benjamina Gonzalez-Flor and Assoc. Prof. Djuara Lubis, which was also very meaningful. I appreciate it. Thank you very much for your kindness and support.

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Abstract

This study explored the interactions between organizational communication (OC), knowledge management (KM), and learning organization (LO) in a senior high school in Malang, Indonesia. A mixed method approach was employed to determine the associations of OC practices on the development of KM processes in an LO. Quantitative analysis using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used to determine significant relationships between OC, KM and LO variables. Interpretation of an interview, on the other hand, was used to analyze transcript to draw qualitative insights from.

Results showed a strong correlation between OC and KM processes. Effective communication channels facilitated knowledge sharing, acquisition, and dissemination of information among stakeholders in the secondary school. Moreover, the integration of OC and KM enhanced the development of an LO that promoted adaptability, continuous improvement, and overall educational effectiveness. Key mediating factors such as leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student involvement played an important role in strengthening the OC-KM-LO relationship.

The study emphasizes the need to link communication strategies with KM initiatives to promote institutional learning and innovation in education. Recommendations for practitioners include fostering a culture of open communication, investing in technology-driven KM platforms, and strengthening leadership capacity to support institutional change. This study advances the theoretical and practical understanding of organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization principles in education and provides valuable insights for improving teaching, learning, and administrative practices in secondary schools.

Keywords: *organizational communication, knowledge management, learning organization, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, thematic analysis, leadership support, technology infrastructure, teacher-student engagement*

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background and Rationale of the Study

In recent years, the educational landscape has undergone a significant transformation, emphasizing the roles of organizational communication and knowledge management in fostering effective learning environments. Senior high schools, as pivotal components of the education system, increasingly recognize the need to align their practices with the principles of learning organizations. These organizations are characterized by a culture that promotes continuous learning, knowledge-sharing, and adaptability.

Organizational communication is the linchpin in facilitating the exchange of information, ideas, and knowledge within educational institutions. Clear and transparent communication are fundamental for creating a collaborative environment among teachers, administrators, and students. Thus, effective communication ensures the smooth operation of daily activities and plays a critical role in shaping the institution's culture.

Effective information management is paramount in educational settings due to the diverse types of information schools need. These include academic records, student assessments, curriculum materials, administrative documents, communication records, and learning resources. According to Chu et al. (2011), managing this multifaceted information landscape is essential for promoting efficiency, facilitating informed decision-making, and ensuring the smooth operation of various educational processes.

Organizational communication also significantly shapes the learning environment within educational institutions, particularly in the dynamic context of senior high schools in Indonesia. Effective communication facilitates knowledge exchange and contributes to developing a learning organization where adaptability, continuous improvement, and knowledge management are integral.

Understanding the intricacies of organizational communication and its relation to knowledge management and the concept of a learning organization within senior high schools is therefore paramount. Knowledge management involves systematically creating, capturing, organizing, and applying knowledge to enhance teaching methodologies and institutional processes. It goes beyond mere information preservation to active utilization for continuous improvement.

While the importance of organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization in educational settings is acknowledged, a noticeable gap exists in understanding how these three components synergize to create a conducive educational environment.

The specific practices, challenges, and opportunities at the intersection of organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization within the unique context of an Indonesian high school remain understudied. Most existing studies focused on either communication or knowledge management separately, leaving a gap in understanding their integration and effectiveness in high schools much more the concept of a learning organization.

The case in point is St. Josef Senior High School where knowledge management, organizational communication, and as a learning organization are

critical in harnessing the collective expertise of educators and administrators. KM practices involve systematically capturing, organizing, and applying knowledge to enhance teaching methodologies and institutional processes. The school's commitment to learning is intricately tied to how it manages and leverages its intellectual assets. Thus, this study aimed to bridge this knowledge gap by examining how knowledge management, organizational communication, and learning organization practices, ultimately create a senior high school that is conducive for learners to grow to become a productive citizen of the world.

Statement of the Problem

Organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization practices are essential in any entity like high schools. The contemporary educational landscape is marked by rapid technological advancements, necessitating a comprehensive examination of how these three functions can lead to survival of secondary schools. Despite the recognized importance of these elements, a gap persists in understanding the interplay and impact on the overall learning experience within a school setting.

The exchange of information, sharing knowledge and educational resources, and the ability to learn continuously within the school premises is critical especially for new teachers and those who are about to retire. The tacit knowledge among older faculty members due to their long and rich experience is worth capturing through KM. However, if a faculty member for instance is not willing to share that tacit knowledge, where does the burden lie? Can the faculty member be faulted? How can the practice

be nurtured towards developing into a learning organization? How should members of the organizations communicate?

Thus, in general, the study aimed to answer the question: What are the associations between learning organization, organizational communication, and knowledge management?

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do current organizational communication practices in a senior high school in Malang, Indonesia facilitate or hinder effective knowledge management practices?
2. How do organizational communication channels contribute to or impede the flow of information, knowledge acquisition, and sharing among stakeholders in a high school setting?
3. How does the integration of organizational communication and knowledge management affect the development of a learning organization like St Josef High School?; and
4. What role do leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement play in mediating the relationship between organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization in St. Josef High School?

Objectives of the Study

In general, the study aimed to analyze associations between learning organization, organizational communication, and knowledge management.

Specifically, the study attempted to:

1. Determine the current organizational communication practices in a senior high school in Malang, Indonesia that facilitate or hinder effective knowledge management practices;
2. Explain how organizational communication channels contribute to or impede the flow of information, knowledge acquisition, and sharing among stakeholders in a high school setting;
3. Examine the effects of the integration of organizational communication and knowledge management in the development of a learning organization like St Josef High School; and
4. Analyze the role of leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement in mediating the relationship between organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization in St. Josef High School.

Significance of the Study

This research holds paramount significance in several dimensions. Firstly, it contributes to organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization by offering insights into their interplay within the unique setting of senior

high schools. Understanding how communication and knowledge flow in this context is crucial for improving educational processes.

Secondly, the study addresses the practical implications of integrating knowledge management practices within the organizational communication framework. Identifying specific needs and challenges in the Indonesian senior high school system can guide policymakers, educators, and administrators in enhancing educational practices.

Furthermore, the research's significance extends to the global discourse on learning organizations. By investigating the role of organizational communication and knowledge management, the study can provide valuable lessons and best practices applicable to Malang and similar educational institutions worldwide.

This research is fundamental in the context of senior high schools in Indonesia, as it directly addresses the need to enhance the educational environment. By focusing on knowledge management and communication, it strives to improve the quality of education, which is vital for students' academic development and future success.

The study's emphasis on learning organization concepts is crucial in a rapidly changing world where adaptability, continuous improvement, and knowledge dissemination are essential. By exploring and promoting these concepts, the research contributes to the long-term growth of educational institutions.

The research contributes to the academic understanding of organizational communication and knowledge management in educational settings, potentially leading to further research. It builds a foundation for future studies on learning organization principles within high schools.

The study aligns with global trends in education, which increasingly emphasize adaptability, technology integration, and knowledge management. Senior high schools in Indonesia can benefit from adopting practices aligned with international educational developments. A robust education system is fundamental to a country's competitiveness. Findings and recommendations can potentially strengthen the Indonesian education sector, making it more competitive on a global scale.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The purpose of this chapter is to review the current literature related to organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organizations. Following this review, the chapter presents the theoretical model and conceptual framework used in this mixed-method study, which explores the associations among organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization.

Review of Related Literature

Organizational communication is the critical spark in the circular system that sustains the life of an educational institution, ensuring a seamless flow of information, collaboration, and shared goals. Communication is one of the critical functions in educational management and one of the management functions (Fiedler, 2007). Communication theory depends on the idea that human behavior is linked to the environment, including the past experiences, current conditions and future expectations of all parties involved in communicating information (Duncan, 1973). This theory assumes that the reliability of communication depends on the process by which messages are sent and received.

The synergy between organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization is fundamental in shaping the context of academic settings, especially senior high schools. Organizational communication is the lifeblood of an educational institution and facilitates effective interaction among various stakeholders, including students, teachers, administrators, and parents. Clear and transparent

communication is critical to disseminating information, aligning goals, and creating a collaborative environment conducive to learning.

Organizational Communication

The study of organizational communication has evolved through two significant periods: from 1900 to 1970 and from 1970 to the present. Between 1900 and 1970, concepts and theories primarily drew on Traditional Rhetoric Doctrine, Human Relations Theory, and Organizational Management Theory. Recent developments in organizational communication were influenced by entrepreneurial and industrial communication (1920s-1950s) and the human relations school (1950s-mid-1970s) (Putnam, Phillips, & Chapman, 2004). By the late 1970s, theoretical approaches expanded to include Modern or Empirical Theory, Naturalistic Theory, and Critical Theory, viewing communication as a tool to achieve organizational objectives (Ergin & Birol, 2005).

In the 1980s, organizational communication research shifted, though it maintained some continuity with previous theories. New theoretical currents like Naturalistic Theory and Critical Theory emerged, emphasizing the pluralistic and ideological nature of communication within organizations. Critical Theory, rooted in dialectical materialism, saw organizations as arenas of conflict, with communication serving to mask material realities and perpetuate false consciousness among managers and workers.

The 1990s introduced Postmodern Narrative Theory and Team-Based Management Theory. Postmodern Narrative Theory identified three fundamental narratives: the postmodern condition, the pastiche economy, and the simulacrum.

These perspectives reinterpreted organizations as living, open systems, influencing communication practices significantly (Ergin & Birol,2005).

Organizational communication is the process of information exchange within an organization. Effective communication is critical to the transfer of knowledge, the creation of a shared vision, and the coordination of actions toward common goals. In an organization, however, a unilinear model of communication will not suffice nor interactional. A transactional model at the very least may help but a systems thinking or looking at communication as constitutive works best. Without communication there will be no organization. Therefore, recent research emphasizes the essential role of organizational communication in facilitating the seamless flow of information in educational institutions. As highlighted by Smith and Mounter (2008), effective communication is a critical component of sharing information among administrators, teachers, students, and parents. Facilitating collaboration among various stakeholders within an educational institution is essential. A seamless flow of information is necessary to ensure that all educational community members are well-informed, aligned with organizational goals, and involved in decision-making.

Recent studies highlight the importance of internal communication for teacher satisfaction and institutional effectiveness. For instance, Brinia et al. (2022) emphasized that effective communication systems within schools can drive better institutional performance by enhancing teacher satisfaction and fostering a collaborative environment. Open and transparent communication channels contribute to the establishment of a positive and supportive organizational culture. Clear, timely, and inclusive communication enhances trust among stakeholders, creating an environment conducive to effective teaching and learning.

Moreover, the role of communication in leadership within educational settings has been a focus of recent studies (Glover & Brown, 2019). Influential leaders recognized the significance of communication in articulating a compelling vision, setting expectations, and motivating the educational community. By establishing robust communication channels, leaders create a sense of shared purpose and direction, which is fundamental for the success of any academic institution.

The advent of digital communication tools has also been a notable area of exploration in recent research (Martínez-Santana et al., 2022). As educational institutions embrace technology, understanding how digital communication platforms influence information flow and collaboration has become imperative. Integrating these tools effectively into the communication framework can enhance accessibility, responsiveness, and efficiency.

Digital platforms and collaborative tools have become integral components, enabling instant communication among students, faculty, and administrators. Real-time updates, announcements, and policy changes are disseminated efficiently, fostering a well-informed and connected educational community. Platforms facilitating virtual meetings, shared documents, and collaborative projects contribute to a sense of shared purpose and collective efficacy among educational professionals.

Virtual collaboration spaces, online forums, and shared document repositories support transparent communication and collaboration in an educational context. The role of technology in facilitating transparent communication among educators has been a critical focus of recent research (Hew & Brush, 2007).

As well, studies also emphasized the importance of transparent communication channels in promoting a culture of collaboration among educators. As complex organizations, educational institutions benefit greatly from a collaborative culture that

allows teachers to share insights, resources, and best practices. Transparent communication channels play a pivotal role in creating an environment that encourages open dialogue and exchange of ideas among educators.

Research has shown that student outcomes tend to improve when educators belong to a collaborative culture (Bryk et al., 2015). Transparent communication lets teachers be fully informed about each other's methodologies, challenges, and successes. As a result, they can share goals, better understand each other's teaching approaches, and create a collaborative community of practice (Inan & Lowther, 2010).

The research by Brinia et al. (2022) underscored the importance of effective communication in enhancing the performance and satisfaction within educational organizations. By establishing clear, transparent, and efficient communication channels, schools can improve not only teacher satisfaction but also overall institutional effectiveness. This study provided valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers aiming to foster a more collaborative and effective educational environment.

Furthermore, the transparency of communication channels is closely tied to trust within the educational community. Trust is nurtured when educators feel that information is shared openly and honestly, contributing to a positive and cohesive work environment (Bormann et al., 2021). Trust is foundational for effective collaboration, and it empowers educators to experiment with new teaching strategies, seek advice, and engage in reflective practices collectively.

Recent global events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have highlighted the importance of organizational communication in crisis management. Clear and timely communication about safety measures and changes in academic delivery has been crucial for maintaining trust and well-being (Brinia et al., 2022).

In the contemporary landscape of organizational dynamics, there is an escalating emphasis on data-driven decision-making, propelling a discernible trend toward measuring the effectiveness of communication strategies. Researchers have engaged in developing metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) tailored to assess the multifaceted dimensions of communication effectiveness. These metrics span various facets, including but not limited to message reach, audience engagement, and the resonance of communication with organizational objectives. By establishing these metrics, organizations can gain a granular understanding of the efficacy of their communication strategies, thereby informing strategic refinements and optimizations.

Organizational communication within high schools has been recognized as a critical element influencing various aspects of the educational environment. Scholars have explored the formal and informal structures that shape communication within these organizations. According to Silin and Mulford (2002), understanding the formal communication structures, such as hierarchies and reporting lines, is crucial for deciphering how information flows within educational institutions. This insight is pivotal for educators, administrators, and policymakers seeking to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of communication processes.

What is more, studies have delved into the role of informal communication channels in senior high schools. Informal communication, often characterized by interactions in staff rooms, hallway conversations, and collaborative teacher activities, play a significant role in shaping the culture and social fabric of educational institutions (Johnson & Majewska, 2022). Researchers have highlighted the need to recognize and leverage these informal channels for effective communication and knowledge sharing among educators.

Communication patterns within the senior high school have been the subject of considerable investigation. Scholars have explored how different communication styles and preferences among educators impact collaboration and decision-making processes. For instance, Morrison (2011) highlights the diverse communication patterns among teaching staff and emphasizes the importance of fostering a communication culture accommodating this diversity. Senge (2000) emphasizes the importance of effective communication in promoting learning organizations where shared visions and continuous learning are valued. Organizational communication theory provides a framework for understanding how information flows within educational institutions. The question then would be how are these communication processes or information dissemination documented? What steps or strategies are being employed to capture, store, and retrieve those information? A more systematic process of capturing these explicit and tacit knowledge disseminated would be through knowledge management.

Knowledge Management

KM has developed in recent years as a dynamic symbiosis between science and art and has significantly impacted business and education. It functions within corporate governance but focuses on intangible resources. Peter F. Drucker was one of the first visionary writers to foresee the emergence of a new economy driven by knowledge. He wrote: "In recent decades, knowledge has become the economy's main capital, cost centre, and a key resource. It is changing the meaning of labor and work, education and learning, knowledge and its policies" and coined the terms 'knowledge economy,' 'knowledge work,' and 'knowledge workers' for this new economy. In the

new economy, knowledge is conceived of as a resource for production with different characteristics from the usual tangible resources.

KM involves creating, sharing, and using knowledge within an organization. It is an integral part of organizational learning and innovation. Fundamental theories and concepts of knowledge management include (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995) the following:

- a. Nonaka-Takeuchi SECI model focuses on knowledge creation through socialization, externalization, combination and internalization. It emphasizes the role of interaction and communication in transforming tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge.
- b. Knowledge management cycle consists of knowledge creation, storage, retrieval, transfer and application. Effective communication plays a vital role in each stage.
- c. Communities of practice: communities of practice are groups of individuals who share knowledge and expertise. They rely on solid interpersonal communication for tacit knowledge exchange.

KM in high schools involves the systematic capture and dissemination of both explicit and tacit knowledge. Explicit knowledge includes written procedures and curricular materials that are organized and made accessible to facilitate seamless knowledge transfer. Tacit knowledge, on the other hand, is tacitly internalized knowledge that individuals accumulate through experience, insight and personal reflection.

In the educational context, this includes an intuitive understanding of effective teaching methods, the complexity of learners' needs and the unwritten rules governing the learning environment. Tacit knowledge is a silent authority that exists in the minds of educators, administrators, and students. It is an essential but often overlooked aspect of educational practice.

It is important to be aware of the subtle importance of tacit knowledge and its role in shaping everyday practices in academic institutions. Educators intuitively use tacit knowledge in their daily classroom practice. For example, experienced teachers' ability to gauge students' emotional states, anticipate potential difficulties and adapt teaching strategies that rely heavily on tacit knowledge. Such tacit wisdom is manifested in the fluidity with which educators navigate complex classroom dynamics. A recent study by Hansen et al. (1999) further emphasized the importance of tacit knowledge in fostering organizational innovation and adaptability.

The ability to navigate the intricacies of interpersonal relationships and organizational dynamics relies on this implicit reservoir of wisdom. Tacit knowledge is not confined to educators and administrators; students, too, possess their own set of tacit knowledge. This includes their individual learning preferences, coping mechanisms, and the unspoken challenges they might face.

Educators who tune into this tacit dimension can tailor their teaching approaches to better resonate with students' intuitive understanding of their learning processes. One of the distinctive features of tacit knowledge is its informal transfer within the educational ecosystem. While formal training and explicit knowledge transfer occur through structured channels, tacit knowledge often flows organically through conversations, collaborative projects, and shared experiences. Educators sharing insights during a casual discussion or students collaboratively solving a problem contribute to the continuous exchange of tacit knowledge.

Despite its significance, capturing and codifying tacit knowledge pose challenges. This type of knowledge is deeply personal and context-specific, making it resistant to formal documentation. Organizations seeking to harness tacit knowledge must explore innovative approaches, such as mentorship programs, collaborative

learning communities, and storytelling platforms to facilitate its transfer. As educators and institutions navigate the ever-evolving landscape of education, understanding and leveraging the power of tacit knowledge becomes integral in fostering continuous improvement and meaningful learning experiences.

The multifaceted nature of KM within senior high schools is illuminated in studies that delve into its various dimensions. Knowledge in this context encompasses not only explicit information but also tacit insights residing in the minds of educators, administrators, and students. This holistic approach acknowledges the diverse forms of knowledge contributing to the richness of educational practices (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995).

In the evolving education paradigm, KM is recognized as a linchpin for fostering effective teaching methodologies, informed decision-making, and a culture of continuous improvement. This perspective aligns with the broader shift toward acknowledging educational institutions as dynamic entities that can leverage knowledge as a strategic asset.

Recent studies have shed light on the critical role of KM in the educational domain, particularly emphasizing its significance within senior high schools aspiring to embody the characteristics of a learning organization. This examination delves into the essential findings and insights derived from these studies, providing a comprehensive understanding of the pivotal role that knowledge management plays in shaping the educational landscape.

A seminal study by Argote and Ingram (2000) delved into the dynamics of knowledge transfer and its impact on organizational learning. Within the educational milieu, this implies that effective KM practices can facilitate the seamless sharing of

pedagogical insights, best practices, and innovative teaching methodologies among educators.

Effective KM practices enable schools to leverage their collective expertise, thus, improving teaching quality and administrative efficiency. The integration of KM into educational settings has been shown to enhance both academic and operational outcomes. For instance, a study by Firmansyah et al. (2022) highlighted the role of KM in vocational schools, demonstrating how it contributed to improved performance in the digital era by facilitating better decision-making and innovation.

This knowledge circulation fosters a collaborative environment conducive to continuous improvement. From fostering knowledge creation and sharing to integrating with learning organization principles and enhancing teaching methodologies, effective KM practices emerge as catalysts for positive educational transformation.

In the educational context, high schools that embrace KM aligned with the principles of learning organizations by prioritizing the systematic management of knowledge to improve teaching practices and student outcomes. Moreover, recent studies have illuminated the transformative impact of KM on organizational learning within senior high schools. Chourides et al. (2003) investigated how KM created a knowledge-centric culture, where information is archived and actively utilized to enhance decision-making processes.

This aligns with the evolving narrative that effective KM is not solely about accumulation but leveraging institutional knowledge to elevate teaching methodologies and decision-making processes (Dalkir, 2013). Wenger, McDermott, and Snyder (2002) discussed Communities of Practice (CoP) in educational settings,

where knowledge is created and shared collaboratively. Effective KM enhances decision-making and contributes to developing a learning organization.

One of the primary findings from recent studies is the emphasis on knowledge creation and sharing as fundamental components of effective knowledge management in senior high schools. Researchers have explored how creating new knowledge, often through collaborative efforts among educators, contributed to a dynamic and innovative learning environment. The sharing of this knowledge is seen as a crucial mechanism for disseminating best practices and fostering a culture of continuous learning among teachers.

A seminal work in this context is the study by Hargreaves and Fullan (2012), which emphasizes the role of collaborative professionalism in educational settings. The authors argued that teachers become active agents of positive change in their schools through collaborative knowledge creation and sharing. This aligns with the broader narrative of teachers as lifelong learners and contributors to developing a vibrant and innovative educational ecosystem.

In the realm of education, the creation of new knowledge often emerges from collaborative efforts among teachers who share diverse experiences, pedagogical approaches, and subject-specific insights. This collaborative knowledge creation aligns with the principles of a learning organization, where the emphasis is not only on individual expertise but on the collective intelligence of the teaching community (Senge, 1990). This collaborative model of knowledge creation is fundamental to addressing the multifaceted challenges and opportunities within the educational landscape. The generation of new knowledge is recognized as a key driver for cultivating dynamic and innovative learning environments in school. Scholars highlight

the significance of educators engaging in collaborative endeavours to create insights that go beyond individual expertise, contributing to a richer educational landscape.

Knowledge creation within senior high schools involves acquiring explicit information and cultivating an environment that encourages innovation, critical thinking, and the synthesis of new insights. This aligns with Nonaka and Takeuchi's (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995) concept of "tacit knowledge," emphasizing the value of experiential and context-specific insights that educators, administrators, and students bring to the learning environment.

Sharing newly created knowledge is crucial for disseminating best practices and fostering a culture of continuous learning among teachers. It goes beyond the traditional professional development model by encouraging a more organic and peer-driven approach to education. Teachers actively sharing their insights, successes, and challenges contributes to creating a communal knowledge repository, enriching the professional growth of the entire teaching community. Research by Little (2003) shed light on "teacher learning in community," emphasizing the transformative power of teachers coming together to create and share knowledge. Little argued that such collaborative efforts benefitted individual teachers and contributed to improving teaching practices and student outcomes.

Effective KM is instrumental in ensuring that the wealth of valuable insights and best practices within the high school is preserved and strategically leveraged to enhance teaching methodologies and institutional processes. Topical studies emphasized the transformative impact of knowledge utilization, shedding light on how educational institutions can move beyond mere preservation to actively extracting value from their accumulated knowledge.

KM Integration with Learning Organization Principles

KM involves the systematic process of capturing, organizing, and applying both explicit and tacit knowledge within an organization. In the context of organizational learning, effective knowledge management becomes the backbone, ensuring that insights gained from experiences are not only preserved but also strategically leveraged to foster continuous improvement.

Recent research highlights the fundamental link between knowledge management practices and learning organization principles. High schools seeking to develop a learning organizational culture use knowledge management as a strategic tool. This integration involves aligning knowledge management processes with the core principles of a learning organization, such as promoting continuous learning, adaptive change, and shared vision.

Moreover, recent research emphasizes the transformative impact of KM on organizational learning. Notable literature in this regard is the work of Alavi and Leidner (2001) who proposed a socio-technical framework for understanding KM. According to their model, effective knowledge creation and sharing integrates both technological tools and social processes. High schools can utilize digital platforms, collaboration tools, and communication channels to facilitate seamless knowledge sharing between educators and students. In parallel, recent research highlighted the dynamic interplay between knowledge management and organizational learning.

As organizations accumulate knowledge assets, KM practices will play a key role in effectively disseminating these products across teams and creating a more informed and adaptive learning environment. This involves systematically identifying, developing, and disseminating knowledge assets within an organization. In senior high schools, this includes the explicit knowledge contained in textbooks and curricula and

the management of tacit knowledge embedded in the experience and expertise of teachers and staff.

OC and KM create a dynamic ecosystem where information flows seamlessly and knowledge is harnessed for continuous improvement. For instance, transparent communication channels facilitate the sharing of innovative teaching practices, while knowledge management systems ensure that these practices are documented, accessible, and incorporated into the educational framework. This collaborative approach aligns with the principles of a learning organization, where adaptability, continuous improvement, and knowledge utilization are integral components.

A seminal study by Argote and Ingram (2000) delved into the dynamics of knowledge transfer and its impact on organizational learning. Within the educational milieu, this implies that effective KM practices can facilitate the seamless sharing of pedagogical insights, best practices, and innovative teaching methodologies among educators. This knowledge circulation fosters a collaborative environment conducive to continuous improvement. The evolving concept of learning organizations accentuates the significance of KM within senior high schools.

As expounded by Senge (1990), learning organizations are entities that actively promote learning at all levels, valuing the acquisition and application of knowledge. In the educational context, high schools that embrace KM align with the principles of learning organizations by prioritizing the systematic management of knowledge to improve teaching practices and student outcomes.

Moreover, recent studies have illuminated the transformative impact of KM on organizational learning within high schools. An investigation by Chourides et al. (2003) underscored how KM contributed to the creation of a knowledge-centric culture, where information is not merely archived but actively utilized to enhance decision-making

processes. This aligns with the evolving narrative that effective KM is not solely about accumulation but about leveraging institutional knowledge to elevate teaching methodologies and decision-making processes (Dalkir, 2013). Concisely, the recent discourse on KM in senior high schools emphasizes its indispensable role in fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement. The literature underscores the need for a comprehensive approach that encompasses explicit and tacit knowledge, aligns with the principles of learning organizations, and actively contributes to the transformative impact of education.

Organizational Culture as KM Infrastructure

In an organizational context, KM infrastructure includes five major components:

- organizational culture
- organizational structure
- organisation's information technology infrastructure
- common knowledge, and
- physical environment (Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal, 2010).

Organizational culture reflects the norms and beliefs that guide the behavior of the organization's members. It is an essential enabler of KM in organizations. Attributes of enabling organizational culture include understanding the value of knowledge management practices, managing support for KM at all levels, incentives that reward knowledge-sharing, and encouragement of interaction for the creation and sharing of knowledge (Ambrect et al., 2001 as cited in Becerra-Fernandez and Sabherwal, 2010).

Furthermore, KM goes beyond mere knowledge accumulation and actively promotes a culture of continuous learning and adaptation. The cyclical nature of KM, where insights from past decisions are reflected in future decisions, creates a dynamic

and responsive learning environment. This iterative learning process is designed to address challenges, seize opportunities and optimize strategies for student learning.

Essentially, the integration of KM into education is a strategic move that transforms decision-making from a routine administrative task into a transformative force that propels organizations towards excellence. By harnessing the power of knowledge, educational leaders are able to make decisions that positively impact not only the direct functioning of their institutions, but most importantly the holistic learning experience of their students.

INNO (Knowledge management and innovation)

Contemporary studies in educational research bring attention to the transformative impact of knowledge utilization within academic institutions, particularly in the context of higher education, not senior high schools. Moving beyond the conventional understanding of knowledge as a preserved asset, these studies delved into how institutions can actively extract value from their accumulated knowledge, fostering innovation, informed decision-making, and continuous improvement. Knowledge utilization catalyzes innovation within educational institutions. Instead of static repositories, institutions become dynamic hubs where accumulated knowledge is actively applied to address challenges and seize opportunities. This shift is crucial in an era where adaptability and innovation are keys to educational success.

One research in Vietnam, for example, the authors of this study have found that KM comprehensively impacts technical INNO (Knowledge management and innovation) in academic settings and that not all components of KM are directly associated with administrative INNO (Ngoc-Tan Nguyen and Gregar, 2018). Besides enriching the literature on this, this study is also of value in managerial perspective as

it helps increase higher education institutions' (HEIs) knowledge on how to boost their organizational innovativeness, and then enhance performance by engaging in KM activities. Last but not least, knowledge management is vital for developing organizational learning phenomena which lead to learning organizations.

Learning Organization

The learning organization (LO) concept has evolved significantly, reflecting dynamic changes in organizational structures, leadership paradigms and the broader socio-economic context. An LO is an adaptive organization that constantly evolves based on experience and insight (Argote, 2012).

The roots of the learning organization concept date back to the 20th century. Learning organizations proactively seek new knowledge, adapt to change, and improve processes. Popularized by Peter Senge, this concept involves creating an environment where learning is embedded in the organisation's DNA. Senge introduced the idea of an organization that fosters continuous learning and adaptation in his seminal work *The Fifth Discipline*. Senge's framework emphasized systems thinking, individual mastery, mental models, shared vision, and team learning as essential elements of a learning organization. Over the years, this foundational work has laid the foundation for subsequent developments in the field.

Organizational learning is creating, retaining, and transferring knowledge within an organization. It evolves as the organization gains experience. From this experience, knowledge can be gained. An LO prioritizes continuous learning, adaptability, and innovation. To create an LO, theories and models emphasize the importance of organizational culture and communication. Fundamental theories and concepts include:

1. Senge's Five Disciplines: Peter Senge's disciplines include personal mastery, mental models, shared vision, team learning, and systems thinking. Effective communication supports the development of these disciplines. According to Senge, "A learning organization is a place where people continually discover how they create their reality. And how they change it" (Senge, 1990, p. 13). A learning organization develops the second loop of learning and generative learning based on entropic, nonlinear, probabilistic, intelligent, and creative thinking. Knowledge is a strategic resource; knowledge management integrates any organisation's operational and strategic perspectives. Knowledge strategies are designed to reduce knowledge absence and create generative knowledge that contributes directly to business sustainability in a changing environment.
2. Argyris and Schön's Single-Loop and Double-Loop Learning: Learning organizations engage in double-loop learning, which involves questioning underlying assumptions. Transparent communication is vital for this process.
3. Garvin's Three Building Blocks of a Learning Organization: These blocks are a supportive learning environment, concrete learning processes and practices, and leadership that reinforces learning. Effective communication is integral to each block.

In the contemporary organizational landscape, an LO has become a strategic imperative for businesses navigating complex and fast-paced environments. Digital transformation has played a pivotal role, with organizations integrating technologies like artificial intelligence and data analytics to enhance learning processes.

Leadership, particularly transformational leadership, is recognized as a critical factor in cultivating a learning culture.

Peter Senge's seminal work, "The Fifth Discipline: The Art & Practice of The Learning Organization," published in 1990, as quoted before, has significantly influenced how organizations approach learning and development. The 2023 edition of this book continues to build on Senge's foundational concepts, incorporating over 15 years of practical applications and updates from contemporary organizational practices (Senge, 2023). This updated edition includes new tools and frameworks organizations can use to assess their learning environment and drive continuous improvement.

The concept of LO is critical for educational institutions aiming to adapt to changing environments and foster continuous improvement. Recent literature continues to build on these foundations, arguing that educational institutions must embrace these disciplines to remain competitive and effective.

Research emphasizes the reciprocal relationship between employee engagement and organizational learning, highlighting the importance of a motivated and committed workforce in driving continuous learning. KM practices contribute to this adaptability by fostering a culture of constant improvement. Studies revealed how effective knowledge-sharing and utilization lead to informed decision-making, innovative teaching methodologies, and an overall culture of intellectual curiosity within senior high schools.

In the high school context, this notion became foundational for understanding the role of educational institutions as dynamic entities that evolve through collective learning. Before 2020, scholars like Argyris and Schön (1978) laid the theoretical groundwork for organizational learning. High schools were conceptualized as

environments where educators, students, and administrators continuously acquire, interpret, and apply knowledge. This perspective was foundational in connecting the principles of learning organizations to the educational landscape.

Early works in organizational communication set the stage for understanding communication as a sense-making process. In learning organizations within high schools, effective communication was recognized as essential for fostering collaboration, disseminating knowledge, and creating a shared vision for continuous improvement. The collaborative exchange of pedagogical strategies, successful teaching methodologies, and subject-specific insights contributes to a dynamic learning ecosystem in the educational domain.

This resonates with the principles of a learning organization, where knowledge is not confined but actively circulated among stakeholders (Senge, 1990). Garvin, Edmondson, and Gino (2008) emphasized that learning organizations foster an environment where collective learning is prioritized, aligning closely with the goals of senior high schools in Indonesia. This groundwork knowledge has been essential for shaping subsequent research and interventions in educational organizational development.

Learning Organization and Organizational Learning

While LO is an entity that prioritizes and facilitates continuous learning and adaptation, it is characterized by a culture that encourages employees to acquire and share knowledge, fostering innovation and adaptability. Additionally, organizational learning is a process within a company or an organization where knowledge is acquired, shared, and applied to enhance effectiveness.

It is a broader term encompassing the systematic acquisition of knowledge, skills, and insights at the organizational level. Organizational learning involves individuals and the collective understanding of the entire entity. It often consists of the identification of errors, adjustments based on feedback, and the development of routines that contribute to improved performance.

LOs have similarities and differences. Similarities include:

- Continuous Improvement: Both concepts emphasize the importance of ongoing improvement. In a learning organization and through organizational learning, there is a commitment to continuous development and enhancement.
- Knowledge-sharing: Central to both is the sharing of knowledge. Employees are encouraged to share insights, experiences, and expertise to benefit the organization.
- Adaptability: LOs and organizational learning promote adaptability. They recognize the importance of being flexible and responsive to changes in the external environment.

Differences are as follows:

- Focus and Scope: The primary difference lies in the focus and scope. An LO is more about the overall culture and ethos that promotes learning. On the other hand, organisational learning is a specific process or set of activities geared towards acquiring and applying knowledge.
- Individual vs. Collective: Organizational learning often involves the organisation's collective learning. LOs may focus more on individual and collective knowledge, but the emphasis is on creating a culture where learning is pervasive.

- Structural vs. Cultural: Organizational learning can be seen as a structural aspect involving processes and systems for learning. LOs, however, are more about the cultural aspect, emphasizing the values and mindset that encourage learning.

In summary, while organizational learning is a process within an organization, a learning organization represents a holistic approach where learning is deeply ingrained in the organizational culture. They complement each other, with organizational learning being one of the mechanisms through which a learning organization operates. A learning organization represents a transformative and holistic approach to organizational learning, where the very fabric of the organizational culture is infused with a commitment to learning at all levels.

At its essence, an LO is characterized by several fundamental principles (Senge, 2023):

1. System Thinking: A fundamental tenet of a learning organization is system thinking, where individuals view the organization as an interconnected and interdependent system. This holistic perspective encourages employees to understand the broader implications of their actions and decisions on the organization.
2. Shared Vision: Learning organizations are united by a shared vision that goes beyond individual goals. This shared vision serves as a guiding force, aligning the efforts of individuals and teams toward common objectives and fostering a sense of purpose.
3. Personal Mastery: Emphasizing personal mastery, a learning organization encourages individuals to develop their skills and expertise continuously. This

commitment to personal growth aligns with the belief that its members' continuous improvement bolsters the organisation's collective strength.

4. **Mental Models:** In a learning organization, there is a recognition that individuals bring diverse mental models—assumptions, beliefs, and perspectives—to the workplace. Encouraging an open dialogue and challenging these mental models fosters creativity and innovation.
5. **Team Learning:** Learning is not confined to individual endeavours but extends to collective team learning. Teams in a learning organization share insights, collaborate on problem-solving, and collectively enhance their capabilities.
6. **Encouraging Innovation:** Learning organizations foster a culture of experimentation and innovation. They understand that failure is an inherent part of the learning process and view it as an opportunity to glean valuable insights for improvement.
7. **Open Communication:** Transparent and open communication is vital in a learning organization. This includes the free flow of information, active listening, and a willingness to share successes and challenges.
8. **Adaptability:** Learning organizations exhibit a high degree of adaptability. They are agile in responding to external environment changes and quickly adjust strategies based on new information.

Previously, LOs represent a paradigm shift in how organizations perceive and approach learning. It goes beyond training programs or occasional workshops; instead, it integrates learning into the organization's fabric, creating a culture where curiosity, collaboration, and adaptability flourish.

A prominent theme in current literature is the integration of KM principles into the fabric of LOs. Scholars emphasized knowledge creation and its effective utilization

for ongoing learning processes. This integration reflects a shift towards more holistic approaches to organizational learning, where knowledge is a dynamic and strategic asset.

LOs, particularly within the context of senior high schools, has been a subject of scholarly exploration, laying the groundwork for understanding its intricate connections to KM and OC. In reviewing the literature predating 2020, key themes and insights emerged, shaping the understanding of how educational institutions foster learning, manage knowledge, and communicate effectively.

Theoretical Constructs

Based on a thorough review of the literature in the first phase, it is clear that there is a deep and complex triadic relationship between OC, KM, and LO. The interaction of these dimensions forms a dynamic and interdependent framework that significantly influences the functioning and effectiveness of an organization, especially in the context of educational institutions.

By developing a theoretical model to illuminate the complex interactions between OC, KM, and LO, the study employed critical organizational and management concepts to provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the complex dynamics in educational settings such as senior high schools. Building a theoretical model requires a visual representation of the relationships between key concepts.

A triangle connecting three concepts with a double-headed arrow is an appropriate representation in a correlational model, where all variables are interrelated without explicit causal relationships. In this theoretical model, this study assumed a triangle representing the interrelationship of three key concepts: OC, KM, and LO.

Figure 1. *Relationships of knowledge management, organizational communication, and learning organization in a senior high school*

This theoretical model could be explicated as follows:

OC positioned at one vertex of the triangle of the theoretical model is depicted as a dynamic and reciprocal force influencing and being influenced by KM and LO. It represents the organisational context's flow of information, messages, and interactions. OC serves as the connective tissue within the theoretical model. It is the medium through which knowledge is shared, and learning is facilitated. Effective communication channels, both formal and informal, contribute to the dissemination of information critical for KM and the learning process (Shockley-Zalabak, 2012).

KM, another vertex of the triangle theoretical model illustrates its integral relationship with OC and LO. KM involves creating, sharing, and applying knowledge within the organization, contributing to a continuous learning environment. It is positioned as a critical beneficiary of an effective OC. Open and transparent communication channels facilitate the sharing of tacit and explicit knowledge. Conversely, successful KM practices create a knowledge-rich environment supporting organizational learning. The model asserts that organizational culture significantly impacts the effectiveness of KM initiatives. For instance, a culture that values

innovation and collaboration will likely facilitate the creation and sharing of knowledge among educators and administrators. KM practices, in turn, contribute to the preservation and dissemination of the cultural values and tacit knowledge embedded in an organization (Alavi & Leidner, 2001).

In tandem with this, KM practices are instrumental in capturing, organizing, and disseminating the wealth of implicit and explicit knowledge inherent in an educational setting. This reservoir of knowledge becomes a catalyst for organizational learning, where the institution evolves and adapts based on insights gained from experiences, successes, and challenges. The synergy among these elements forms a comprehensive triad, where effective communication channels and a conducive organizational culture propel knowledge management initiatives, fostering a continuous cycle of learning and improvement.

LO, the third vertex of the triangle theoretical model represents Learning Organization, indicating its close association with OC and KM. LO involves acquiring, interpreting, and applying knowledge to enhance the organization's overall capacity for adaptation and innovation. LO is the outcome of effective OC and KM. Communication facilitates the flow of insights and lessons learned, contributing to LO. Simultaneously, KM ensures that the learning process is systematic, capturing, and disseminating knowledge for continuous improvement.

The model posits that both OC and KM influence LO. Organizational communication that promotes continuous learning and adaptation supports the organization in acquiring new knowledge. Simultaneously, effective KM practices contribute to accessing relevant information, fostering a learning environment where insights are readily available to inform decision-making and improve practices (Argyris and Schön, 1978).

The absence of directional arrows indicates that causation is not implied, recognizing the complex and bidirectional nature of relationships among these critical organizational components. The model asserts bidirectional relationships. Effective OC fosters successful KM by creating a culture where information flows seamlessly. KM, in turn, supports organizational learning by providing the infrastructure for capturing and applying knowledge gained through communication and experience.

The double-headed arrows between each pair of concepts emphasize these variables' reciprocal and interconnected nature. Changes in OC are linked to changes in both KM and LO, and *vice versa*. Similarly, changes in KM are correlated with changes in OC and LO. More importantly, this correlational model reflects that no variable is strictly independent or dependent of each other.

In correlational studies, the focus shifts from the traditional distinction between independent and dependent variables, a characteristic more commonly associated with experimental research designs. Instead, correlational studies investigate relationships between variables without asserting a cause-and-effect relationship. This approach is particularly relevant when researchers aim to understand the degree of association between two or more variables.

In this correlational model, double-headed arrows imply correlation, indicating that changes in one variable are associated with changes in the other but do not imply a directional causal relationship. While these concepts are interrelated, it does not necessarily mean that studying their relationships is impossible or invalid. Examining how these interconnected elements influence each other is a common and valuable approach in organizational studies.

In this context, there are no predefined independent or dependent variables; all the identified variables are considered equally. The rationale behind this design is rooted in exploring natural relationships in real-world settings. For instance, in a study examining the correlation between student engagement and academic performance, both variables are considered equally crucial without assigning one as independent and the other as dependent.

Correlation coefficients, often represented by the symbol 'r,' quantify the strength and direction of associations between variables. The values of 'r' range from -1 to +1, where -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, +1 represents a perfect positive correlation, and 0 denotes no correlation. For example, in a study exploring the correlation between organizational communication effectiveness and employee job satisfaction, the researchers may use a correlation coefficient to assess the strength and direction of the relationship.

If 'r' is close to +1, it suggests a positive correlation, indicating that job satisfaction increases as organisational communication effectiveness rises. It is crucial to note that correlation studies do not imply causation. Establishing a correlation between two variables does not prove that changes in one variable cause changes in the other. Instead, it highlights patterns and associations, promoting further investigation.

This theoretical model serves as a visual guide to understanding the interconnected dynamics of OC, KM, and LO in a correlation framework within the organizational context. The correlation among these three dimensions is not linear but a complex interplay. Communication acts as the vehicle through which knowledge is disseminated, fostering a culture of organizational learning. In turn, learning

organization enhances the efficacy of KM systems, creating a cyclical and reinforcing relationship.

Understanding and harnessing this three-way correlation is paramount for educational institutions. A communication strategy that aligns with KM initiatives can optimize the utilization of intellectual capital. Concurrently, organizational learning practices refine communication strategies and enhance KM systems.

The three-way correlation between OC, KM, and LO is discernible in organizational dynamics and forms the foundation for organizational success. Acknowledging and strategically navigating these interconnected dimensions can empower educational institutions to cultivate an environment conducive to growth, innovation, and sustained excellence.

This theoretical model underscores organizations' need to invest in communication strategies that promote transparency and KM practices that capture and disseminate information. The synergy between these elements creates a fertile ground for learning organization, enabling adaptability, and innovation.

In the context of a senior high school, this theoretical model has practical implications. Leaders can intentionally cultivate a culture that values collaboration, innovation, and continuous learning. KM strategies can then align with this culture, ensuring valuable insights are captured, shared, and leveraged for educational improvement.

Numerous studies underscore the significance of this three-way correlation, highlighting how a harmonized OC strategy, a nurturing organizational culture, and robust KM processes collectively contribute to establishing a vibrant learning organization. Through this intricate interconnection, educational institutions can cultivate an environment where information flows seamlessly, knowledge is harnessed

for continuous improvement, and the institution evolves into a dynamic hub of learning and innovation.

Conceptual Framework

In this study, the conceptual framework created a theoretical blueprint, illustrating the connections and interactions between the critical dimensions of OC, KM, and LO. The study assumed that OC, KM, and LO interact within an organizational context and that they are correlated which means no one dimension causes another. The associations are so intertwined that the existence of one is indispensable in looking at how an organization functions as a whole such as a senior high school.

Essentially, these concepts are deeply intertwined in a symbiotic relationship where effective communication supports knowledge processes, and a learning organization leverages both communication and knowledge for continuous improvement, as elaborated as follows:

1. **OC** represents the flow of information, ideas, and interactions within the organization. This includes formal channels such as official memos and reports and informal channels like conversations and social interactions among staff. The empirical referents for OC within the senior high school refer to the concrete practices, systems, and behaviors such as weekly staff meetings to review progress on school improvement plans and address any immediate concerns. It encompasses a variety of practices and systems that ensure effective information exchange and collaboration among stakeholders. By understanding and implementing these concrete practices, high schools can enhance their OC, leading to improved educational outcomes and a more

cohesive school community. In this study, OC can be operationalized as levels of transparency, communication tools use satisfaction, communication clarity, two-way communication, and frequency of using communication channels.

Levels of transparency in OC refers to the perceived clarity and openness of communication within the senior high school. Transparency can be observed through interactions among staff and administrators, the accessibility of information, and the extent to which decisions and processes are communicated openly. This was measured by assessing the respondents' perceptions of the school's clarity and openness of communication. Likert-scale questions were used to rate the transparency of communication on a scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Communication tools satisfaction assessed how satisfied are staff and administrators with the communication tools and platforms used within the senior high school, such as emails, messaging apps, and other communication software. This was observed by monitoring the usage patterns of communication tools, gathering feedback from staff and administrators about their experiences with these tools, and identifying any challenges or issues encountered. It was measured through survey questions that asked respondents to rate their level of satisfaction with each tool using a Likert scale, where responses range from very dissatisfied to very satisfied.

Communication clarity refers to the extent to which messages communicated within the senior high school are clear, concise, and easily understood by recipients. Communication exchanges among staff and administrators were observed paying attention to the clarity of verbal and written communication, the use of jargon or technical language, and the effectiveness of message

delivery. This was measured using survey questions that asked respondents to rate communication within the school on a Likert scale, where responses range from very unclear to very clear.

Two-Way Communication assessed the extent to which there is a two-way flow of communication within the senior high school, emphasizing feedback mechanisms and responsiveness. It involved assessing the degree of interaction and engagement in communication exchanges, opportunities for feedback and dialogue, and stakeholders' responsiveness to communication. This was measured through survey questions that asked respondents to rate the extent to which they felt their voices were heard and valued within the school's communication processes.

Frequency of communication channels refers to the rate with which various communication channels are utilized within the senior high school, such as staff meetings, emails, newsletters, and messaging apps. This was measured by tracking the occurrence of staff meetings, the volume of emails sent and received, the publication frequency of newsletters, and messaging apps analytics. Questions using a likert scale were employed to rate the frequency of communication channels on a scale from always to never.

2. **KM** signifies the processes involved in creating, sharing, and applying knowledge within an organization. It consists of capturing tacit knowledge from individuals, documenting explicit knowledge, and fostering a culture that values and leverages collective knowledge. The empirical referent for KM delves into the concrete practices and systems organizations employ to capture, store, and disseminate knowledge. It encompasses the design and functionality of knowledge repositories, the frequency and methods of knowledge-sharing

sessions, and the utilization of technology for knowledge transfer. In a real-world context, it involves examining how employees collaborate, document their expertise, and leverage available knowledge resources in their day-to-day activities. KM in the context of a senior high school involves defining and measuring critical components related to the creation, sharing, and utilization of knowledge within the educational setting, such as:

- Knowledge documentation: assessed how knowledge is documented and stored within the school using databases, digital platforms, or traditional filing systems;
- Knowledge-sharing practices: measured the effectiveness of knowledge-sharing practices among teachers, staff, and administrators, including formal and informal mechanisms for sharing insights, experiences, and best practices;
- Knowledge accessibility: evaluated the ease with which individuals within the school can access and retrieve relevant knowledge when needed, considering information availability, retrieval systems, and barriers to access;
- Knowledge transfer and training: explored the strategies and effectiveness of knowledge transfer and training programs within the school, including professional development initiatives, mentoring programs, and knowledge transfer workshops.
- KM practices: refers to systematic processes and strategies implemented to acquire, create, share, and utilize knowledge effectively within the educational environment. These variables were observed based on how information flows within the school, looked at documentation practices,

information sharing during meetings, and the use of digital platforms, and identified key individuals who acted as knowledge hubs. These were measured by quantifying the creation and utilization of knowledge artefacts such as lesson plans, best practices documents, and collaborative projects.

3. **LO** embodies the organization's ability to adapt, innovate, and improve based on the insights gained from both internal and external sources. It encompasses individual and collective learning, promoting a culture of continuous improvement. In a senior high school context, it involves regular professional development workshops, collaborative learning communities among teachers, and a shared vision for student success that guides decision-making and curriculum development. The empirical referent is rooted in the adaptive behaviors, knowledge acquisition processes, and the actualization of learning initiatives within the organization. It involved scrutinizing how lessons from past experiences were integrated into decision-making processes, the extent to which training programs are implemented, and the organization's overall agility in responding to external changes. In this case, the empirical referent is manifested in the observable ways the organization evolves and incorporates new insights.

Effective OC facilitates the success of KM initiatives, while the insights gained contribute to the learning culture within the organization. Similarly, an LO is shaped by both OC practices and KM strategies. By recognizing the interdependence of these variables, organizations can develop more holistic strategies for fostering a culture of

continuous learning and innovation. The empirical level of the model brings these theoretical abstractions into practical applicability. For instance, **interconnected realities** are crucial to note that these empirical referents are not isolated entities but interlinked aspects of the organizational landscape. How knowledge is managed directly influences the organisation's learning capacity, and both are intricately woven into the fabric of the organizational culture.

The interactions between these empirical referents create a complex tapestry that researchers navigate to understand how OC, KM, and LO collectively contribute to the vitality and adaptability of an organization. Exploring empirical referents goes beyond theoretical abstraction, offering practical insights for organizations seeking to enhance their organizational communication, knowledge processes, and learning initiatives. By examining these empirical dimensions, researchers and organizational leaders can pinpoint areas for improvement, innovation, and sustainable growth, ensuring that theoretical constructs are not confined to academic discourse but resonate in the tangible realities of the organizational world.

In this study, the counterpart or empirical referent of OC, KM, and LO, lies in the daily functioning and interactions within the real-world context of a senior high school. The practical manifestation of these concepts is observed in the communication channels, knowledge utilization, and learning mechanisms that shape the dynamics of an educational institution. These indicators and measures were tested to determine the associations in each dimension.

Figure 2. Relationships of knowledge management, organizational communication, and learning organization in a senior high school

Hypotheses

Subsequently, the following hypotheses were tested as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Hypotheses of the study (H0)

OC ↔ KM	OC ↔ LO	KM ↔ LO
<p>1. Hypotheses for correlation between OC and KM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Levels of transparency in OC positively correlate with knowledge documentation practices. • Satisfaction with communication tools positively 	<p>2. Hypotheses for correlation between OC and LO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The frequency of using communication channels is positively correlated with personal mastery. • Transparency is positively 	<p>3. Hypotheses for correlation between KM and LO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge documentation is positively correlated with personal mastery. • Knowledge-sharing is positively

OC ↔ KM	OC ↔ LO	KM ↔ LO
<p>correlates with knowledge-sharing within the organization.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication clarity is positively associated with knowledge transfer and training practices. • Two-way communication is positively correlated with the effectiveness of KM practices. • The frequency of using communication channels positively correlates with knowledge accessibility. 	<p>correlated with shared vision.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction with communication tools is positively correlated with team learning. • Communication clarity is positively correlated with the mental model. • Two-way communication is positively correlated with the decision-making process. 	<p>correlated with shared vision.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The effectiveness of KM practices is positively correlated with team learning. • Knowledge accessibility is positively correlated with mental model. • Knowledge transfer and training are positively correlated with decision-making processes.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication clarity is positively associated with knowledge documentation. • Communication clarity is positively associated with the effectiveness of KM practices. • Communication clarity is positively associated with knowledge-sharing. • Communication clarity is positively associated with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The frequency of using communication channels is positively associated with shared vision. • The frequency of using communication channels is positively associated with team learning. • The frequency of communication channels is positively 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge documentation is positively correlated with shared vision. • Knowledge documentation is positively correlated with team learning. • Knowledge documentation is positively correlated with mental model. • Knowledge documentation is positively

OC ↔ KM	OC ↔ LO	KM ↔ LO
<p>knowledge accessibility.</p>	<p>associated with the mental model.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The frequency of using communication channels is positively associated with the decision-making process. 	<p>correlated with decision-making processes.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Levels of transparency in OC positively correlate with knowledge accessibility. Levels of transparency in OC positively correlate with knowledge-sharing. Levels of transparency in OC positively correlate with KM practices. Levels of transparency in OC positively correlate with knowledge transfer and training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transparency in communication positively correlates with team learning. Transparency in communication positively correlates with mental models. Transparency in communication positively correlates with decision-making processes. Transparency in communication positively correlates with personal mastery. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge-sharing is positively correlated with personal mastery. Knowledge-sharing is positively correlated with team learning. Knowledge-sharing is positively correlated with mental model. Knowledge-sharing is positively correlated with decision-making processes.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two-way communication is positively correlated with knowledge documentation. Two-way communication is positively 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satisfaction with communication tools is positively correlated with mental models. Satisfaction with communication tools is positively correlated with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The effectiveness of KM practices is positively correlated with shared vision. The effectiveness of KM practices is positively correlated with personal mastery.

OC ↔ KM	OC ↔ LO	KM ↔ LO
<p>correlated with knowledge-sharing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two-way communication is positively correlated with Knowledge transfer and training. Two-way communication is positively correlated with knowledge accessibility. 	<p>decision-making processes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satisfaction with communication tools is positively correlated with personal mastery. Satisfaction with communication tools is positively correlated with shared vision. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The effectiveness of KM practices is positively correlated with mental model. The effectiveness of KM practices is positively correlated with decision-making processes.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The frequency of using communication channels positively correlates with knowledge ocumentation. The frequency of using communication channels positively correlates with knowledge-sharing. The frequency of using communication channels positively correlates with knowledge transfer and training. The frequency of communication channels positively correlates with the effectiveness of KM practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication clarity is positively correlated with shared vision. Communication clarity is positively correlated with personal mastery. Communication clarity is positively correlated with decision-making processes. Communication clarity is positively correlated with team learning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge accessibility is positively correlated with shared vision. Knowledge accessibility is positively correlated with personal mastery. Knowledge accessibility is positively correlated with decision-making processes. Knowledge accessibility is positively correlated with team learning.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased satisfaction with communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two-way communication is positively 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge transfer and training are

OC ↔ KM	OC ↔ LO	KM ↔ LO
<p>tools positively correlates with knowledge documentation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased satisfaction with communication tools positively correlates with knowledge transfer and training. • Increased satisfaction with communication tools positively correlates with the effectiveness of KM practices. • Increased satisfaction with communication tools positively correlates with knowledge accessibility. 	<p>correlated with mental model.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two-way communication is positively correlated with team learning. • Two-way communication is positively correlated with personal mastery. • Two-way communication is positively correlated with shared vision. 	<p>positively correlated with shared vision.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer and training are positively correlated with personal mastery. • Knowledge transfer and training are positively correlated with team learning. • Knowledge transfer and training are positively correlated with mental model.

Operational Definition of Terms

Organizational Communication

refers to the exchange of information, ideas, and messages within the senior high school setting. It involves verbal and written interactions, digital platforms, and communication tools to facilitate collaboration, disseminate information, and foster a conducive learning environment. It

encompasses formal and informal communication processes among stakeholders, including administrators, teachers, students, and support staff. OC has five indicators, namely; frequency of using communication channels measured in terms of staff meetings, emails, newsletters, and messaging apps. A likert scale was used to measure the frequency of using the communication channels with bipolar adjectives from always to never.

Knowledge Management

involves the processes and strategies used to capture, create, store, and distribute knowledge within an organization. This was measured in terms of knowledge documentation within the school using databases, digital platforms, or traditional filing systems.

Knowledge-sharing practices

refer to how teachers, staff, and administrators, including formal and informal mechanisms for sharing insights, experiences, and best practices.

Knowledge Accessibility

Evaluate the ease with which individuals within the school can access and retrieve

relevant knowledge when needed, considering information availability, retrieval systems, and barriers to access.

Knowledge Transfer and Training

Explore the strategies and effectiveness of knowledge transfer and training programs within the school, including professional development initiatives, mentoring programs, and knowledge transfer workshops.

KM Practices

refers to systematic processes and strategies implemented to acquire, create, share, and utilize knowledge effectively within the educational environment.

Learning Organization

can be defined as a senior high school that fosters a culture of continuous learning, innovation, and improvement among its members. It is an educational institution that values and actively promotes acquiring, creating, sharing, and applying knowledge and skills to achieve its educational goals and objectives. A learning organization in the senior high school context is characterized by a dynamic, adaptive, and innovative learning culture that enables the school to

respond effectively to challenges, embrace change, and achieve sustainable excellence in education. This was measured in terms of personal mastery, shared vision, team learning, and mental model. Personal mastery encourages and support educators, staff, and students to continuously develop and enhance their skills, expertise, and capabilities.

Shared Vision

Establishing a common vision and goals communicated and embraced by all stakeholders, fostering alignment and unity of purpose.

Team Learning

Promoting collaborative learning and problem-solving among teaching teams, administrative staff, and students, enabling collective intelligence and synergy.

Mental Models

Challenging and expanding the underlying assumptions, beliefs, and paradigms held by individuals within the school community to foster open-mindedness and creativity.

Decision-Making

Encouraging a holistic understanding of the interconnectedness and interdependencies within the educational system, enabling

informed decision-making and systemic improvement.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a convergent parallel mixed methods research design. This design involves collecting both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, analyzing each data set separately, and then comparing the results to see if the findings confirm or contradict each other (Creswell & Plano-Clark, 2011). The convergent parallel design allows the researcher to triangulate the results by directly comparing and contrasting quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings for validation and interpretation.

The quantitative component involved administering a survey to a large sample of teachers to gather data on their perceptions and experiences regarding communication, knowledge management, and learning organization practices within the school. The qualitative component involved conducting semi-structured interviews with a smaller, purposively selected sample of teachers to gain in-depth insights into their experiences and perceptions. Quantitative methods provide statistical generalizability and allow for the testing of hypotheses, while qualitative methods offer in-depth exploration, context, and the ability to capture diverse perspectives.

An integrated design provides flexibility in data collection methods and analysis techniques, allowing researchers to tailor their approach to the specific research questions and objectives. This adaptability is essential when studying dynamic phenomena such as organizational change and educational innovation.

Figure 3. *Convergent Parallel Mixed Methods Research*

This approach emphasizes the complementary nature of quantitative and qualitative methods and seeks to integrate them from the outset. It, again, facilitates a seamless integration of quantitative and qualitative data, allowing for a comprehensive analysis that goes beyond what each method can achieve alone. Integrated mixed methods research offers a robust and flexible approach to data collection, analysis, and interpretation, allowing researchers to understand complex research problems holistically.

Unlike sequential or parallel designs, where qualitative and quantitative data are analyzed separately and compared, integrated mixed methods research merges the two data types from the outset, creating a synergistic approach to data analysis and interpretation.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at St Josef Senior High School in Malang (*in Bahasa: SMAK Santo Yusup College* and the acronym Kosayu, better known as Hua Ind). The school was officially founded on January 4, 1954. At that time, 1 class (Senior High School Part B) was opened with only 27 students. SM-RK/Catholic People's High

School (now SDK) Hua Ind was previously specifically for Indonesian citizens of Chinese descent. This is because, in the past, Indonesian citizens of Chinese descent were not allowed to study in public schools.

Until now, Hua Ind has developed into one of Indonesia's most favourite "A" accredited national private schools. This school is open to residents of Chinese descent and Indonesian citizens because Hua Ind does not apply the terms indigenous and non-indigenous.

Research Instruments

Qualitative and quantitative data were gathered simultaneously, analyzed the two datasets separately, and interpreted the findings by comparing and integrating the results.

Quantitative Data Collection Phase and One-Shot Survey:

For the quantitative aspect of this research, a one-shot survey involves collecting data at a single point in time. A survey instrument with closed-ended questions or structured scales to gather numerical data was constructed (see on Appendix A). This consisted of questions about organizational communication, knowledge management practices, and perceptions of organizational learning in the senior high school.

Respondents and Participants

The school provided a list of participants which were randomly chosen after the the objectives of this research were explained to teachers and the school principal as the key informants.

Qualitative Data Collection Phase and Interview Guide:

An interview guide (Appendix B) was developed to determine the main topics related to organizational communication, knowledge management, and organizational learning that were explored. Open-ended questions are meant to encourage participants to share their thoughts, experiences, and perceptions. Also, probes or prompts to encourage elaboration or clarification on specific points were raised but not leading questions.

Data Analysis

Examining qualitative and quantitative data within the context of a case study employing the integrated mixed methods research, involves a systematic and phased approach. Incorporating Spearman's Rho for measuring correlation in the quantitative phase and thematic analysis in the qualitative phase provides a comprehensive understanding of the phenomena under investigation. Thematic analysis in the qualitative phase and Spearman's Rho in the quantitative phase contributed to a thorough understanding of the research problem.

The iterative nature of this method allows for a dynamic interaction between data collection, analysis, and interpretation, enhancing the rigour and depth of the overall research study.

Utilizing Spearman's Rho in Measuring Correlation

On the other hand, quantitative data analysis, selecting an appropriate statistical method, is pivotal in research design, particularly when assessing the correlation between variables. In this context, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient,

often denoted as Spearman's Rho, emerges as a valuable tool (Hunsberger et al., 2022).

It was employed to evaluate relationships between variables when the assumption of normal distribution is not met or when dealing with ordinal data. Spearman's Rho is a non-parametric measure, meaning it does not assume a specific distribution for the variables under study. This makes it versatile and applicable in scenarios where the data might not adhere to a normal distribution. The rank-based nature of this method is particularly advantageous when dealing with ordinal or non-interval data. Unlike Pearson's correlation, which measures linear relationships, Spearman's rho is used for both ordinal data and continuous data that do not necessarily have a linear relationship (Rosner & Glynn, 2017).

In the quantitative phase, Spearman's Rho is a valuable tool for assessing the strength and direction of monotonic relationships between variables. The process involves ranking the data, calculating the differences between ranks, and applying Spearman's Rho formula (Salkind, 2010). Spearman's Rho is particularly valuable in scenarios where the assumptions of linearity and normality are not met.

Its non-parametric nature allows for data analysis that may not conform to the assumptions of parametric methods, making it applicable to a wide range of research contexts. Spearman's Rho is less sensitive to outliers than the Pearson correlation coefficient. This robustness makes it a reliable choice when dealing with datasets that may contain extreme values or when the assumption of normality cannot be ensured.

Ordinal data, which involves categories with a meaningful order but lacks a precise numerical distinction between them, is a common scenario where Spearman's rank correlation finds its utility. Examples of ordinal data include survey responses with

ordered categories like "strongly disagree," "disagree," "neutral," "agree," and "strongly agree." In such cases, using Spearman's Rho allows researchers to analyze the association between variables without assuming that the intervals between categories are equal.

Moreover, when dealing with datasets that do not meet the assumptions of linearity and normality, Spearman's rank correlation provides a robust alternative.

Spearman's Rho is calculated by assigning ranks to each variable's values and then determining the correlation between the ranked variables. The formula for Spearman's Rho involves computing the difference between the paired ranks and applying a correction for ties, producing a coefficient that ranges from -1 to 1.

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Here, ρ represents Spearman's Rho, d_i is the difference between the paired ranks, and n is the number of observations. A positive ρ indicates a monotonic relationship, while a negative ρ indicates a negative one.

This method is well-suited for ordinal or ranked data, making it relevant when the variables under investigation represent categories with a meaningful order but lack a consistent interval scale. Examples include survey responses or academic rankings. Spearman's Rho finds applications across various disciplines, including psychology, sociology, and biology, where researchers seek to understand relationships between variables without imposing stringent assumptions on the data distribution.

Interpretation of Qualitative Responses

In the qualitative domain of this research, where richness of insight and depth of understanding are crucial, interpretation is emerging as a robust method for making

meaning from interview transcripts. This approach provided a systematic and flexible method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns in the data.

In the context of the study on organizational communication culture, knowledge management, and organizational learning within senior high school in Malang, Indonesia, interpretation serves several crucial purposes. It allows us to explore participants' narratives, unveiling the intricate connections between communication practices, knowledge-sharing dynamics, and the overall learning ethos of the organization.

By identifying dominant themes, it helped to support the hypotheses by grounding them in the lived experiences and perspectives of those within the educational context. Themes may emerge around effective communication strategies, challenges in knowledge dissemination, or the tangible impact of these practices on the learning environment.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Current OC system that facilitate or hinder effective KM practices

The current organizational communication at St Josef High School that could either facilitate or hinder effective knowledge management practices were determined. OC includes frequency of using communication channels such as staff meetings, emails, and messaging apps. It also involved transparency in terms of perceived clarity and openness of communication within the school. It was also imperative to gauge how satisfied were the faculty and staff of the school as far as online communication tools were concerned. The clarity and conciseness of messages communicated was also a critical component for KM practices to be put in place. The type of communication model plays a critical role and in this case, knowing to what extent of at least a two-way communication flows within the school, emphasizing feedback mechanisms and responsiveness. These variables as measures of OC were tested in determining their association with KM practices. KM variables, on the other hand, include: knowledge accessibility or the ease of accessing and retrieving relevant knowledge. It also delved on knowledge transfer and training strategies. KM processes were also deemed important such as systematic strategies in acquiring, creating, sharing, and utilizing knowledge. Similarly, the study assumed that for KM processes to prosper, these have to be documented or know how the school documents and stores knowledge because if knowledge is not disseminated or shared then it remains to be data, thus, knowledge-sharing practices among teachers, staff, and administrators were likewise measured. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, often denoted as Spearman's Rho was employed to determine relationships between variables. Unlike Pearson's correlation, which measures linear relationships,

Spearman's rho is used for both ordinal data and continuous data that do not necessarily have a linear relationship (Rosner & Glynn, 2017).

The variables that were correlated then for this objective are as follows where OC variables are designated as VAR while KM ones are labelled as VER:

OC Variables:

- VAR1: Frequency of using communication channels
- VAR2: Transparency
- VAR3: Satisfaction with communication tools used
- VAR4: Communication clarity
- VAR5: Two-way communication

KM Variables:

- VER1: Knowledge accessibility
- VER2: Knowledge transfer and training
- VER3: Knowledge management practices
- VER4: Knowledge documentation
- VER5: Knowledge-sharing practices

Through a survey, 69 out of 85 teachers and staff of St. Josef High School responded. Using a five-point Likert scale, respondents were asked to rate their **frequency of using communication channels (VAR1)** whether always, often, neutral, sometimes, and never. Always means every time there is a meeting they attended. Often, on the other hand, is used when meetings happen very frequently but not always. The question to be rated was: how often do you participate in regular staff meetings where vital information is conveyed or communicated. Results showed that 68.1 percent either attended often or always (**Figure 4**). This alludes that they are well-informed and perhaps, updated on what is happening in the school given their attendance in these communication platforms.

Figure 4. Frequency of using communication channels

For **VAR2** or **transparency**, respondents were asked to answer the question: to what extent do you feel that you are well-informed about important decisions and changes the school is implementing. Results revealed that 82.6 percent (**Figure 5**) of respondents either often or always felt that they were well-informed about changes to be implemented. This implies that management is quite transparent in their operations and to make sure that everyone feels included and that nobody is left behind. Perhaps, it is also one way to ensure that dissemination of changes should reach all concerned.

Figure 5. How well-informed respondents feel

Respondents were also asked to rate the question: how satisfied are you with using online-based applications (e.g. RBK=Ruang Belajar Kosayu, Kosayu Study Room, its online communication system) to communicate at school so far using a five-point Likert scale from very satisfied, satisfied, just right, not satisfied, and not very satisfied. Results showed that almost 80 percent (**Figure 6**) were either satisfied or very satisfied. This connotes that online communication platforms were responding to the needs of the users. It may also mean that these online tools are easy to use that is why they are satisfied in using it. Use of technology usually increases if these are easy to use.

Figure 6. Satisfaction with online communication tools used

In terms of communication clarity, respondents answered the question: in your opinion, has the communication process in school been free from ambiguity and misunderstanding. Less than 45 percent (44.9%) said that for the most part, there has been no misunderstanding and ambiguity while almost 40 percent (39.1%) said sometimes it happens in addition to 7.2 percent said that still frequent misunderstanding and ambiguities occurred (**Figure 7**). Perhaps, the way message was crafted may have been vague in terms of the intent. Interpretation may have been left to the teachers and staff.

Figure 7. Communication clarity

For the two-way communication variable, respondents were asked to answer the question: to what extent do you believe your opinions and suggestions are valued and considered in the school's decision-making process. This was rated using a five-point Likert scale with adjectives ranging from very confident, confident, doubtful, not confident, not very confident. Findings showed that more than the majority (55.1%) were confident that their suggestions and opinions were valuable which means that feedback in a two-way communication model is being heard (**Figure 8**). Management should perhaps be mindful of this result because almost 30 percent were doubtful. This is quite a big percentage which may become a management problem if constituents have some feeling of not being heard or just a nobody in an organization.

Figure 8. *Two-way communication*

Knowledge management variables were likewise asked among respondents. VER1 or knowledge accessibility was framed into the question: how quickly can teachers/staff access the information or knowledge to carry out their roles/duties effectively. A five-point Likert scale with adjectives: very quick, quick, not so fast, slow, and very slow were used. Almost 77 percent (76.8%) rated it as quick or fast (**Figure 9**). It seems to appropriate that information in the school is highly accessible which could be supported by the easy use of online communication tools. Suffice to say that the school ensures that everyone has accessed to the information anytime when they need it.

Figure 9. *Knowledge accessibility*

A question on VER2 or knowledge transfer and training was also asked. The question was: how often are training, seminars, workshops and other forms held by the school to ensure the transfer of knowledge and skills to teachers and education staff. A five-point Likert scale was employed with the following ascending adjectives: often enough, often, just right, seldom, and never. Almost 45 percent (44.9%) rated it often and an additional of 36.2 percent saying often enough (**Figure 10**). This seems to show that the school provides ample professional development programs to enhance the competences of their teachers and staff.

Figure 10. *Knowledge transfer and training*

KM variable 3 or knowledge management practices were separately rated through the question: to what extent are digital platforms and technology used for school knowledge management. A five-point Likert scale was used measured as: very widely used, utilized/use, enough to be utilized, not used, not very utilized. Findings to this question showed that almost 60 percent (59.4%) said that digital platforms and technology were used for KM (**Figure 11**).

Figure 11. Knowledge management practices

Using a five-point Likert scale level of agreement, respondents were asked to rate the question: based on your experience, do you agree that various knowledge transfer and training programs in this school have been documented and stored effectively to facilitate the exchange and acquisition of information and expertise among educators and education personnel in the future. Responses showed that a great majority (65.2%) agreed with the statement with 15.9 percent strongly agreeing as well (**Figure 12**). This implies that knowledge transfer and training programs attended or organized have been documented and stored properly for easy retrieval for reuse and perhaps lessons learned. Normally, teachers and staff need this data for promotion or keep tab of those who have been sent to training or can also be a record of expenditures for professional development cost. This may also help in drafting a career development plan or designing the career path and growth of employees of the school to align with institutional outcomes of developing their competences.

Figure 12. Knowledge documentation

The growth of an organization sometimes relies on how people share knowledge from within. In this case, respondents were asked: in your experience, how often do you share knowledge and insights with your colleagues at school. This was measured using a five-point Likert scale with frequencies ranging from always, often, sometimes, seldom, and never. Results showed that almost 60 percent (59.4%) said they shared knowledge and insights with colleagues in the school (**Figure 13**). This seem to imply that relationship among members is collegial where sharing of knowledge is often done which is a good indication of healthy social interactions.

Figure 13. *Knowledge sharing practices*

Correlations of OC and KM

Results of responses to the various questions in OC and KM were correlated to determine association between these two variables. Results of the correlation between **frequency of communication channels (VAR1)** and **sharing practices of KM (VAR5)** showed a high positive correlation (0.322 and significant at 0.007) which suggests that as the frequency of using communication channels increases, there is a corresponding improvement in KM sharing practices. This finding implies that a high school with more open and frequent communication channels is better equipped to implement and leverage KM strategies effectively. Effective and efficient communication channel utilization enhances information flow and facilitates decision-making processes.

Similarly, the statistical analysis unveiled a compelling association between **transparency (VAR2) and knowledge accessibility (VER1)** within the school context, with a remarkable level of statistical significance at 0.01 level. The theoretical framework implies that a robust relationship between transparency in organizational communication positively correlates with knowledge accessibility. This significant correlation underscores the pivotal role of transparency in facilitating knowledge accessibility and dissemination, highlighting its importance as a foundational element of effective knowledge management practices. The strong positive correlation between openness and knowledge accessibility suggests that schools that prioritize transparency tend to have greater accessibility to knowledge resources. Transparency, characterized by openness, honesty, and accountability in organizational processes, creates an environment conducive to knowledge-sharing, collaboration, and innovation.

Transparency cultivates trust and fosters a culture of openness, where information flows freely across organizational boundaries, enabling individuals to access relevant knowledge, resources, and insights. Additionally, the strong association between transparency and knowledge accessibility implies that openness catalyzes effective knowledge management practices. By promoting transparency in decision-making, communication, and resource allocation, schools can break down silos, mitigate information asymmetry, and promote a culture of shared knowledge ownership.

Level-headedly, school leaders and educators should prioritize transparency as a strategic imperative, integrating transparency-enhancing practices into organizational policies, procedures, and communication channels. This may involve promoting open communication channels, providing access to relevant information and resources, and

fostering a climate of trust and accountability. By embracing transparency as a core value and institutionalizing transparency-enhancing practices, schools can create an environment where knowledge flows freely, innovation thrives, and organizational learning flourishes. Ultimately, this contributes to developing a knowledge-rich ecosystem that supports continuous improvement and drives positive educational outcomes.

This significant correlation underscores the pivotal role of transparency in facilitating knowledge accessibility and dissemination, highlighting its importance as a foundational element of effective knowledge management practices. Moreover, the strong association between transparency and knowledge accessibility implies that transparency serves as a catalyst for effective knowledge management practices.

The correlation between **satisfaction with communication tools used (VAR3)** and **KM Practices (VER3)** (0.357 and 0.003) also revealed higher satisfaction levels where use of communication tools are associated with more effective implementation of knowledge management practices within the school. It connotes that when communication tools are perceived positively by staff and stakeholders, they are more likely to engage in activities that facilitate knowledge sharing, creation, and utilization. This significant positive correlation emphasizes the critical role of communication infrastructure in supporting effective knowledge-sharing and utilization within the senior high school.

In like manner, the correlation coefficient between **satisfaction with communication tools use (VAR3)** and **knowledge-sharing practices (VER5)** (0.430 and significant at 0.000) revealed high associations. This result suggests that higher levels of satisfaction with communication tools used are associated with more

robust practices of knowledge-sharing within the school. This could imply that effective communication tools facilitate the dissemination of information and ideas among stakeholders, fostering a culture of collaboration and knowledge exchange. This correlation highlights the pivotal role of communication in fostering a collaborative learning environment within this senior high school. Efforts to enhance communication tools should be aligned with broader strategies to promote knowledge-sharing and collaboration among school community members.

The correlation between **communication clarity (VAR4)** and **knowledge accessibility (VER1)** (0.418 and 0.000) highlights the importance of communication clarity as a foundational element of knowledge management practices in the school. This strong associations implies that communication strategies emphasized clarity and transparency where educational leaders can create an environment conducive to knowledge-sharing and collaboration, ultimately enhancing organizational learning and innovation.

Correlating **communication clarity (VAR4)** and **knowledge documentation (VER4)** (0.398 and 0.001) resulted to strong correlations. This suggests that fostering communication clarity can positively influence the implementation of knowledge documentation systems within educational institutions. Clear communication channels facilitate information dissemination about documentation protocols and encourage staff members to contribute to knowledge repositories. By prioritizing clear communication practices, school leaders can promote a culture of accountability and knowledge stewardship, where information is documented, shared, and utilized effectively.

The correlation between **communication clarity (VAR4)** and **knowledge sharing (VER5)** (0.346 and 0.004) was likewise positively correlated. This indicates that enhancing communication clarity can positively impact the effectiveness of knowledge-sharing initiatives within educational institutions. Clear communication channels facilitate the dissemination of information and ideas, encouraging staff members to contribute their insights and experiences to collective learning efforts. This correlation underscores the importance of fostering a culture of openness and collaboration within the senior high school.

The last variables, **two-way communication (VAR5)** and **KM practices** (0.443 and 0.000) showed that two-way communication enhances the dissemination and utilization of knowledge resources. This finding suggests that as two-way communication channels become more robust and effective, there is a corresponding improvement in the accessibility and availability of knowledge within the learning organization. Two-way communication facilitates the exchange of information, ideas, and expertise among stakeholders, enhancing the dissemination and utilization of knowledge resources. It could explore how two-way communication influences knowledge accessibility and utilization within educational settings.

Effective two-way communication channels are crucial for promoting knowledge-sharing, collaboration, and learning within educational institutions. Schools that prioritize effective communication practices are better equipped to ensure that relevant information and expertise are accessible to all school community members, thereby supporting informed decision-making, problem-solving, and innovation. This correlation highlights the synergistic relationship between OC and KM practices.

It can be surmised therefore that educators and school administrators should recognize the critical role of communication in supporting KM initiatives. They should invest in creating an open and inclusive communication culture, leveraging various channels such as meetings (**Figure 14** as real example of parents meeting with the school management staff), emails, intranet platforms (such as *Ruang Belajar Kosayu* as a management learning system), and social media to facilitate knowledge-sharing and collaboration among teachers, students, and other stakeholders.

Table 2 presents the correlations between OC and KM variables.

Table 2. *Correlations between OC and KM variables*

Hypotheses	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
VAR1 – VER1	0.179	0.142	Reject H0
VAR1 – VER2	-0.016	0.899	Reject H0
VAR1 – VER3	0.237	0.050	Reject H0
VAR1 – VER4	0.079	0.519	Reject H0
VAR1 – VER5	0.322	0.007	Accept H0
VAR2 – VER1	0.357	0.003	Accept H0
VAR2 – VER2	0.060	0.621	Reject H0
VAR2 – VER3	0.214	0.077	Reject H0
VAR2 – VER4	0.238	0.048	Accept H0
VAR2 – VER5	0.307	0.010	Accept H0
VAR3 – VER1	0.264	0.029	Accept H0
VAR3 – VER2	0.229	0.058	Reject H0
VAR3 – VER3	0.452	0.000	Accept H0
VAR3 – VER4	0.195	0.108	Reject H0
VAR3 – VER5	0.430	0.000	Accept H0
VAR4 – VER1	0.418	0.000	Accept H0
VAR4 – VER2	0.469	0.000	Accept H0
VAR4 – VER3	0.422	0.000	Accept H0
VAR4 – VER4	0.398	0.001	Accept H0
VAR4 – VER5	0.346	0.004	Accept H0
VAR5 – VER1	0.464	0.000	Accept H0
VAR5 – VER2	0.306	0.011	Accept H0
VAR5 – VER3	0.443	0.000	Accept H0
VAR5 – VER4	0.353	0.003	Accept H0

Hypotheses	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
VAR5 – VER5	0.411	0.000	Accept H0

These findings are corroborated by the results of the qualitative data participated in by the school principal. This underscores the need for the school to integrate effective communication strategies into their KM framework to optimize learning outcomes, foster innovation, and drive organizational success, including non-formal conversation. It also revealed that non-formal conversations, discussions and chit-chat among staff members and between staff and educators may be more convenient as communication channels in the context of this senior high school.

Figure 14. *Meeting with parents organized by the school*

Current OC system as an LO

The current organizational communication system at St Josef High School is also assumed to be associated with LO. An LO has five dimensions consisting of shared vision or establishing a common vision and goals that all stakeholders embrace. Personal mastery or encouraging continuous development and enhancement of individual skills are requisites for LOs. As an LO, team learning or promoting collaborative learning and problem-solving must be practiced. Since they should work as one, systems thinking or understanding the interconnectedness of

each element within the educational system for informed decision-making strengthens the experience of those working in the school. They are also expected to develop mental models or challenging and expanding underlying beliefs and assumptions about their mandate. In other words, an LO must ensure that its constituents are united and adhere to achieving common goals and objectives and constantly keeping abreast on what is new to improve on current operations or effect changes to the curriculum to respond to the needs of the time. It cannot remain stagnant instead should be dynamic and open to change to survive an increasingly volatile world. The following are the LO variables designated as VIR:

LO Variables:

- VIR1: Shared Vision
- VIR2: Personal Mastery
- VIR3: Team Learning
- VIR4: Decision-Making
- VIR5: Mental Models

Like OC and KM, association with OC and LO was determined using the five variables described. For **VIR1** or **shared vision**, respondents were asked the question: how confident are you that the school's vision and goals are communicated and understood by all teaching and educational staff in this school. Using a five-point Likert scale from very confident, confident, doubtful, not confident, and not very confident, results showed 65.2 percent of respondents said that they were confident in addition to 11.6 percent who rated it as very confident (**Figure 15**). These results seem to imply that the almost all school constituents have learned their vision and goals as an organization. Such action points to the notion that learning organizations have to ensure that everyone is in the loop and that understanding their vision and goals is a must.

Figure 15. *Shared vision communicated and understood*

For **VIR2** or **personal mastery**, respondents were asked to answer the question: I feel that I am constantly improving and mastering new skills in this school for personal growth and development. Using a five-point Likert scale level of agreement from strongly agree, agree, neither agree or disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree, results revealed that a great majority (68.1%) agreed to this statement in addition to 20.3 percent who strongly agreed (Figure 15). This goes to show that they are lifelong learners who are always ready to adapt to better themselves. This could also be a manifestation or proof of training programs that they have attended. The synergy of these actions could probably be the reason why they have developed personal mastery of new skills.

Figure 16. Personal mastery

Team learning or **VIR3** as a measure of an LO was measured using a five-point Likert scale with adjectives ranging from always, often, just right, seldom, and never. Respondents were asked to rate the question: how often do you collaborate with other educators or educational personnel to develop strategies for solving teaching and service student challenges. Results revealed that almost 50 percent (49.3%) said often in addition to the almost 9 percent (8.7%) who said often (**Figure 16**). These results seem to depict that teachers and staff work collaboratively in addressing teaching and student issues which indeed displays a learning organization's characteristics of sharing the burden to improve operations and holistically address that warrant actions. Collaborative learning as a 21st century skill is apparent in the school as proof of continuous improvement of their organization.

Figure 17. Team learning

VIR4 or Decision-Making characterizes an organization that enhances a holistic understanding of the interconnectedness and interdependencies within the educational system, enabling informed decision-making and systemic improvement. This was measured using a five-point Likert scale with varying degrees of involvement such as: involved enough, involved, not much involved, rarely involved, and never. Respondents were asked to rate the question: during this time, how involved are you in the decision-making process in school. More than a third (34.8%) said involved enough in addition to also a third rating it as involved (33.3%) (**Figure 18**). Suffice to say that this result shows a dynamic school organizational structure in terms of decision-making. A system perspective takes into account the role of its parts to achieve synergistic result. In this case, St. Josef High School appears to

apply the systems thinking in managing the school which recognizes the role that teachers and staff plays in achieving its goals and objectives. Thinking as one also implies an open organization that involves its stakeholders in its service delivery by taking into account their wins or losses as they operate daily. The cooperation of one entity depends on the functions of another which makes operations complicated but with a systems perspective, these challenges are readily addressed.

Figure 18. Decision-Making

The last LO variable, **VIR5** or **mental models** refers to challenging and expanding the underlying assumptions, beliefs, and paradigms held by individuals within the school community to foster open-mindedness and creativity. Every individual is unique. When they join an organization, they bring their own world views that may or may not align with that of the institution. Hence, it is crucial to create a common mindset towards a holistic approach in carrying out the school's mission. Mental models if left unattended may break or make an organization. Therefore, for

an LO to continue learning, constituents should embrace the vision and mission of their organization. VIR5 was measured using a five-point scale using the adjectives: strong believe, believe, not sure, do not believe, strongly do not believe.

Respondents were asked to rate the question: to what extent do you believe your assumptions about the learning you teach or the tasks you undertake will influence your actions and decisions in the school environment. A great majority (68.1%) said they believe (**Figure 19**). This rating connotes that teachers and staff take pride that their ideas can influence actions and decision-making in school matters that affect them. As a characteristic of an LO, it goes to show that the school being transparent and collaborative listens to the suggestions of their employees and seems to empower them in the process. An open and warm interaction can lead to camaraderie and a healthy school environment that nourishes personal growth and development. The feeling of being a contributor or influential in decision-making satisfies one's ego and therefore strengthens the commitment to remain in the organization.

Responses: not sure= 7.2%	do not believe= 13%	believe=68.1%
strongly believe=11.6%		

Figure 19. Mental models

Correlations between OC and LO

Results of responses to the various questions in OC and LO were correlated to determine association between these two variables. Results of the correlation between **frequency of communication channels (VAR1)** and **decision-making of LO (VIR4)** showed a high positive correlation (0.250 and significant at 0.038) which suggests that as the frequency of using communication channels increases, there is a corresponding improvement in the involvement of teachers and staff in the decision-making process. This result implies that in an organization, communication is open and involves everyone within the system. This verdict suggests that as the frequency of communication channels increases within the school environment, there is a corresponding enhancement in the decision-making processes, aligning with the principles of a learning organization. The moderate positive correlation signifies that schools with frequent communication channels exhibit more effective and participative decision-making practices.

When **VAR2 or transparency** and **VIR4 or decision-making** were correlated, results showed a positive correlation (0.250 and significant at 0.038). This correlation suggests a meaningful relationship between transparency and the effectiveness of the decision-making process within the organization (as part of System Thinking). Higher levels of transparency tended to be associated with more effective decision-making processes. Transparency in decision-making refers to the extent to which information

is openly shared, clear communication channels, and stakeholders are involved in the decision-making process.

This finding is corroborated by the response of the key informant interviewee, the school principal that shows “an open and transparent communication process can enhance decision-making processes in the school.” He said to wit:

“Sejauh ini, di era kepemimpinan yang saya terapkan terkait keterbukaan dan transparansi komunikasi di sekolah ini dilakukan dengan lebih membangun pada pengelolaan hati. Artinya ada peraturan yang dijadikan sebagai pedoman bersama, tetapi pada pelaksanaannya lebih humanis dengan membangun komunikasi yang dapat menemukan solusi serta komunikasi dengan hati tidak semata-mata dengan menggunakan kekuasaan sebagai pimpinan sekolah. Jadi proses komunikasi harus berjalan dua arah tidak satu arah saja. Kepala sekolah membangun komunikasi yang melibatkan orang dan hati serta menerapkan kepemimpinan yang humanis, Pentingnya mengelola hati untuk taat kepada peraturan. Komunikasi memainkan peran penting dalam pendekatan. Mencari solusi dari setiap perbedaan berdampak setiap kali ada sesuatu yang mungkin tidak pas. Komunikasi harus dibangun secara menyeluruh, termasuk yang vertikal dan horizontal”

(“So far, in the era of leadership that I have implemented regarding openness and transparency of communication in this school, it has been carried out by building more on heart management. This means that there are regulations that serve as shared guidelines. Still, they are more humane in their implementation by creating communication that can find solutions and communicate with the heart, not solely by using power as a school leader. So, the communication process must go both ways, not just one way. The school principal builds communication that involves people and the heart and applies humanist leadership—the importance of managing the heart to obey the rules. Communication plays an important role in the approach. Seeking solutions to any differences has an impact whenever something might not fit. Communication must be built holistically, including vertical and horizontal”)

Heart management implies that operations do not simply run the school like business as usual but a more humane and entrusting organization that prides its social capital as members of a family. This could be unique to the school being sectarian which could have shaped the management style.

VAR3 or satisfaction with online communication tools used and VIR4 or decision-making when correlated resulted to a high positive correlation (0.329 and

significant at 0.006). The positive and statistically significant correlation underscores the pivotal role of communication in facilitating effective governance and decision-making within this senior high school. Improving communication tools and practices should be prioritized to foster a culture of transparency, collaboration, and accountability in decision-making processes.

The correlation of **VAR4 or communication clarity** and **VIR1 or shared vision** revealed a positive correlation (0.326 and significant at 0.006). This result implies that the significant positive correlation highlights the importance of clear communication channels in cultivating organizational alignment and effectiveness within this senior high school. This result indicates that as communication clarity increases, there tends to be a corresponding increase in the presence of a shared vision among stakeholders within the senior high school. This implies that clear and transparent communication channels may facilitate aligning goals, values, and aspirations among individuals and groups, developing and reinforcing a shared vision.

Communication clarity or VAR4 when correlated with **VIR2 or personal mastery** showed a positive correlation (0.340 and significant at 0.004). This result suggest that when messages are clear, teachers and staff would have mastered those. The way messages are crafted will affect how these are perceived and learned. The clearer the messages or information conveyed, the higher the personal mastery. It implies then that unclear messages will not be taken seriously.

The correlation of **VAR4 or communication clarity** and **VIR3 or team learning** also yielded a positive result (0.399 and significant at 0.001). This result implies a meaningful association between communication clarity and team learning practices. The school with clearer communication channels may exhibit higher levels

of team learning, indicating that effective communication fosters collaborative learning environments among team members.

Correlating VAR4 or communication clarity and VIR4 or decision making also yielded a positive correlation (0.391 and significant at 0.001). The statistically significant positive correlation between communication clarity and the decision-making process underscores the pivotal role of clear communication channels in facilitating effective decision-making within this senior high school. There is a robust association between communication clarity and the effectiveness of the decision-making process. Senior high schools with clearer communication channels tend to have more effective decision-making processes, implying that clear communication facilitates better decision-making outcomes. Improving communication clarity within the senior high school can lead to more informed, efficient, and effective decision-making processes. Clear communication fosters understanding, reduces ambiguity, and promotes stakeholder consensus-building, enhancing overall decision-making quality.

VAR4 or communication clarity and VIR5 or mental models are positively correlated (0.373 and significant at 0.001). This relationship highlights the crucial link between communication clarity and the alignment of individuals' mental frameworks. By promoting clarity in communication channels, educational institutions can enhance the coherence of individuals' mental models, leading to greater synergy and collaboration among stakeholders.

Two-way communication or VAR5 was correlated with **VIR1 or shared vision**. The correlation was positive (0.340 and significant at 0.004). This finding underscores the strong relationship between effective two-way communication and the alignment of organizational vision among stakeholders. It seems that the school have feedback mechanisms in place. By prioritizing open dialogue and active

engagement, the school could strengthen organizational cohesion and enhance the collective pursuit of common goals and aspirations.

Correlating **VAR5 or two-way communication** and **VIR2 or personal mastery** also led to a positive correlation (0.257 and significant at 0.031). This implies that two-way interaction provides an opportunity for feedback and discussion in the process which could lead to personal knowledge or mastery of the information imparted. The opportunity to get feedback somehow gives an opportunity for teachers and staff to raise questions or ask clarifications thereby leading to personal mastery. An open communication channel encourages interactions which could lead to common understanding.

The variable **two-way communication or VAR4** was correlated with **VIR3 or team learning** which yielded a positive correlation (0.374 and significant at 0.001). This result implies that two-way communication can enhance collaboration, networking, and linking among teachers and staff. Since interactions are dynamic, they learn from each other leading towards building a healthy and conducive environment for learning.

VAR5 or two-way communication when correlated with **VIR4 or decision-making** were found to be positively correlated (0.376 and significant at 0.001). This finding suggests that as two-way communication channels become more robust and effective, there is a corresponding improvement in the decision-making processes within the learning organization. Enhanced communication allows for better information flow, collaboration, and feedback exchange among stakeholders, leading to more informed and timely decision-making.

Correlating VAR5 or two-way communication and **VIR5 or mental models** had a positive correlation (0.341 and significant at 0.004). This finding suggests that

as two-way communication channels become more robust and effective, there is a corresponding increase in the development and dissemination of mental models within the learning organization. Two-way communication facilitates the exchange of ideas, perspectives, and knowledge among stakeholders, contributing to forming and aligning mental models within the school community.

These results can be further explained by the responses from the key informant, to wit:

“Komunikasi dua arah pasti terbangun dengan baik di SMAK Kolese Santo Yusup, karena dasarnya memang budaya membangun komunikasi dengan hati. Ketika Kepala Sekolah memerlukan tim untuk menyelesaikan tugas khusus, warga sekolah akan siap membantu. Sebaliknya, ketika warga sekolah memerlukan kebijakan khusus, Kepala Sekolah siap mendengarkan dan mencari solusi.

Contoh: Ketika sekolah memiliki pekerjaan khusus kepanitiaan dalam even tertentu, maka tim yang dimintai tolong akan mempersiapkan sebaik mungkin tanpa mempermasalahkan jam kerja. Terkadang harus melanjutkan pekerjaan itu meskipun melebihi jam kerja yang telah disepakati. Ketika karyawan memiliki kepentingan keluarga, maka Kepala Sekolah memberikan izin khusus meskipun melewati ketentuan peraturan. Dan dapat dipastikan guru lain tetap berkenan untuk menggantikan tugas mengajar yang harus ditinggalkan guru tersebut. Tujuan dari menyampaikan informasi tersebut adalah untuk memberikan gambaran kepada pihak luar, seperti orang tua siswa yang ingin menyekolahkan anaknya di sekolah tersebut”

(“Two-way communication is well established at SMAK Santo Yusup College because the basis is a culture of building communication with a heart. When the Principal needs a team to complete a special task, the school community will be ready to help. On the other hand, when the school community needs a special policy, the Principal is prepared to listen and find a solution.

Example: When a school has special committee work for a certain event, the team that is asked for help will prepare as best as possible without worrying about working hours. Sometimes, you must continue the work despite exceeding the agreed working hours. When employees have family interests, the Principal gives special permission even though it violates regulatory requirements. You can also be sure that other teachers will still be willing to take over the teaching duties that the teacher has to leave. This information is intended to provide an overview to outside parties, such as parents of students who want to send their children to that school”)

Table 3 presents the correlations between OC and LO.

Table 3. Correlations between OC and LO

Hypotheses	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
VAR1 – VIR1	0.119	0.332	Reject H0
VAR1 – VIR2	0.039	0.752	Reject H0
VAR1 – VIR3	0.148	0.225	Reject H0
VAR1 – VIR4	0.250	0.038	Accept H0
VAR1 – VIR5	0.078	0.526	Reject H0
VAR2 – VIR1	0.116	0.341	Reject H0
VAR2 – VIR2	0.158	0.194	Reject H0
VAR2 – VIR3	0.221	0.068	Reject H0
VAR2 – VIR4	0.250	0.038	Accept H0
VAR2 – VIR5	0.112	0.358	Reject H0
VAR3 – VIR1	0.136	0.264	Reject H0
VAR3 – VIR2	0.085	0.491	Reject H0
VAR3 – VIR3	0.111	0.362	Reject H0
VAR3 – VIR4	0.329	0.006	Accept H0
VAR3 – VIR5	0.105	0.387	Reject H0
VAR4 – VIR1	0.326	0.006	Accept H0
VAR4 – VIR2	0.340	0.004	Accept H0
VAR4 – VIR3	0.399	0.001	Accept H0
VAR4 – VIR4	0.391	0.001	Accept H0
VAR4 – VIR5	0.373	0.001	Accept H0
VAR5 – VIR1	0.340	0.004	Accept H0
VAR5 – VIR2	0.257	0.032	Accept H0
VAR5 – VIR3	0.374	0.001	Accept H0
VAR5 – VIR4	0.376	0.001	Accept H0
VAR5 – VIR5	0.341	0.004	Accept H0

Correlations between KM and LO

Results of responses to the various questions in KM and LO were correlated to determine association between these two variables. All variables correlated yielded positive correlations. These correlations suggest a moderately strong association between variables. It indicates that schools where knowledge is easily accessible tend

to have a shared vision among staff members regarding the institution's goals, values, and objectives. It implies that when information and resources are readily available, there is a greater likelihood of alignment and coherence in the collective vision and direction of the school community. The significant correlation between knowledge accessibility and shared vision underscores the importance of transparent communication and information sharing in cultivating a cohesive organizational culture. By prioritizing strategies to enhance knowledge accessibility, school leaders can promote a shared understanding and commitment to the school's mission and values among all stakeholders.

Schools where knowledge is easily accessible, tended to have staff members who demonstrate personal mastery in their respective fields. In this context, it suggests that educators with access to knowledge resources are likelier to engage in ongoing professional development and enhance their skills and expertise. This indicates that improving knowledge accessibility can contribute to fostering a culture of continuous learning and professional growth among staff members within educational institutions. Educators with easy access to relevant information and resources are better equipped to pursue opportunities for skill development, innovation, and excellence in their practice.

Statistical analyses revealed a significant positive correlation, which means that schools, where knowledge is readily accessible tended to foster environments conducive to team learning. This suggests that enhancing knowledge accessibility can promote collaborative learning environments within schools. Educators with easy access to information and resources are likelier to engage in cooperative learning activities such as sharing best practices, conducting joint projects, and participating in professional learning communities.

As well, correlations suggest that schools where knowledge is readily accessible, tended to exhibit more effective decision-making processes as part of systems thinking. By promoting a culture of openness and knowledge-sharing, school leaders can empower stakeholders to contribute their expertise and insights to the decision-making process, leading to more informed and effective outcomes.

Similarly, schools where knowledge is easily accessible, tended to be a more developed understanding and alignment of mental models among stakeholders. The strong correlation between knowledge accessibility and mental models implies that when information is readily available and accessible, stakeholders can better align their understanding and perspectives, leading to more cohesive and shared mental models within the school community. This alignment of mental models can foster a sense of common purpose, enhance communication and collaboration, and facilitate decision-making processes.

Having effective knowledge transfer and training practices in place tended to be a stronger alignment with and commitment to a shared vision among stakeholders. The strong correlation between knowledge transfer and training practices and shared vision implies that when schools invest in initiatives to facilitate the sharing and dissemination of knowledge and skills among stakeholders, there is a corresponding enhancement in the clarity and alignment of the school's vision. Effective knowledge transfer and training practices help ensure stakeholders have the necessary knowledge, skills, and understanding to contribute meaningfully to realising the school's vision.

Suffice to say that schools with effective knowledge transfer and training practices are likelier to foster an environment conducive to team learning. The statistically significant correlation between knowledge transfer and training practices

and team learning underscores the importance of integrating these practices into the school's organizational culture and practices. Schools should invest in professional development opportunities, establish knowledge-sharing platforms, and create collaborative spaces where individuals can learn from one another and collectively solve problems.

The school with its effective knowledge transfer and training practices is likelier to facilitate better decision-making processes. Effective training programs and knowledge-sharing initiatives had equipped teachers and staff with the necessary skills, information, and resources to make informed decisions that contributed to the overall success and effectiveness of the organization.

A moderate to strong relationship between the implementation of knowledge transfer and training with mental models within the organization implies that investing in comprehensive training programs that encourage individuals to explore different perspectives, challenge assumptions, and engage in reflective practices can enhance their ability to develop and refine mental models. By fostering a learning environment that values diverse perspectives and encourages open dialogue, the school supported the development of more adaptive and resilient mental models among their stakeholders.

As well, a moderate to strong relationship between implementing effective knowledge management practices and establishing a shared vision among organisational stakeholders showed that prioritising knowledge management practices, such as knowledge-sharing platforms, collaboration tools, and organizational learning initiatives tended to foster a stronger sense of shared vision among staff, students, and administrators. Shared vision is a collective understanding

of the school's mission, values, and goals, guiding decision-making, planning, and action.

With effective knowledge management practices, it is likelier to foster a culture of team learning among their staff and stakeholders. This implies that institutions prioritizing knowledge management, organization, and dissemination are also conducive to collaborative learning environments where teams can collectively share insights, experiences, and best practices to enhance their capabilities.

Hence, with robust knowledge management practices, more effective decision-making processes were exhibited. Institutions prioritizing knowledge management, documentation, and accessibility are better equipped to make informed decisions based on accessible, well-organized information.

Results also suggest that the school with its robust knowledge management practices is likelier to foster a culture where individuals develop shared mental models or understanding of the organization's goals, values, and strategies. This correlation implies that effective knowledge management, including documentation and accessibility, contributes to developing and aligning mental models among stakeholders, thereby enhancing organizational cohesion and alignment.

Knowledge documentation practices will likely have a well-defined and widely understood shared vision among stakeholders. The correlation between knowledge documentation practices and shared vision highlights the crucial role of documentation in shaping organizational identity and direction. It emphasizes the significance of clear and accessible documentation in promoting a sense of purpose and unity among school community members.

Knowledge documentation processes foster an environment conducive to personal mastery among individuals within the organization. Effective knowledge

documentation, including best practices, expertise, and learning resources, can provide individuals with the necessary information and tools to enhance their skills and capabilities.

A meaningful relationship between these variables, imply that as the quality of knowledge documentation practices improves, there is a tendency for decision-making processes to become more effective. This could be attributed to the availability of relevant information and insights stored through documentation, facilitating better-informed decision-making by school administrators and staff.

Also, knowledge documentation practices and the development of mental models among staff and students implies that schools with well-established knowledge documentation systems will likely foster a shared understanding of mental models among their stakeholders. Effective documentation of knowledge and experiences facilitates the creation and disseminating of shared mental models, contributing to improved communication, collaboration, and decision-making within the school environment.

This could be attributed to the fact that knowledge-sharing initiatives and establishing a shared vision among stakeholders within the school community can enhance alignment with vision and goals among individuals within the school.

Results also connotes that the extent to which knowledge-sharing practices are effective and the level of personal mastery demonstrated by individuals within the school community, indicates a meaningful association, implying that as knowledge-sharing practices improve, there tends to be a corresponding enhancement in individuals' ability to develop and apply their skills and competencies effectively.

Knowledge-sharing practices can also enhance the capacity for collective learning and knowledge generation among teams or groups. The significant

correlation between knowledge-sharing practices and team learning highlights the integral role of collaborative learning processes in supporting organizational learning and knowledge generation within the school context. Schools should prioritize initiatives encouraging teamwork, open communication, and mutual support, leveraging their staff and students' collective intelligence and expertise for enhanced educational outcomes.

Improved knowledge-sharing practices also tended to have more effective decision-making processes within the school environment. The strong correlation between knowledge-sharing practices and decision-making processes emphasized the critical role of effective communication and information sharing in supporting organizational effectiveness and adaptability within the senior high school. Thus, the school should prioritize initiatives that promote transparency, inclusivity, and knowledge-sharing to enhance decision-making capabilities and overall organizational performance.

Finally, findings suggest a meaningful relationship to which knowledge is shared within the organization and the formation of mental models among stakeholders. By facilitating the exchange of ideas, experiences, and perspectives, knowledge-sharing practices construct shared mental models that improve collective understanding, decision-making, and problem-solving capabilities. Overall, it can be surmised that KM and LO are correlational where one determines the success of each other. The absence of one can be the downfall of the other. Therefore, putting a KM system in place determines the dynamic growth of a learning organization.

Table 4 presents the correlations between KM and LO.

Table 4. *Correlations between KM and LO*

Hypotheses	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
VER1 – VIR1	0.412	0.000	Accept H0
VER1 – VIR2	0.367	0.002	Accept H0
VER1 – VIR3	0.499	0.000	Accept H0
VER1 – VIR4	0.404	0.001	Accept H0
VER1 – VIR5	0.432	0.000	Accept H0
VER2 – VIR1	0.401	0.001	Accept H0
VER2 – VIR2	0.394	0.001	Accept H0
VER2 – VIR3	0.514	0.000	Accept H0
VER2 – VIR4	0.499	0.000	Accept H0
VER2 – VIR5	0.479	0.000	Accept H0
VER3 – VIR1	0.423	0.000	Accept H0
VER3 – VIR2	0.358	0.003	Accept H0
VER3 – VIR3	0.520	0.000	Accept H0
VER3 – VIR4	0.407	0.001	Accept H0
VER3 – VIR5	0.438	0.000	Accept H0
VER4 – VIR1	0.417	0.000	Accept H0
VER4 – VIR2	0.393	0.001	Accept H0
VER4 – VIR3	0.472	0.000	Accept H0
VER4 – VIR4	0.482	0.000	Accept H0
VER4 – VIR5	0.500	0.000	Accept H0
VER5 – VIR1	0.439	0.000	Accept H0
VER5 – VIR2	0.439	0.000	Accept H0
VER5 – VIR3	0.545	0.000	Accept H0
VER5 – VIR4	0.460	0.000	Accept H0
VER5 – VIR5	0.523	0.000	Accept H0

The results of the interview succinctly captures the positive correlations. He said that:

“Program Diklat Calon Kepala Sekolah. Dalam diklat ini kami megirimkan dua staf pimpinan. Hal ini sangat penting dikerjakan dan hasilnya sangat efektif. Ketika kegiatan berlangsung staf yang lain mengambil alih tugas yang harus ditinggalkan oleh staf peserta diklat. Hingga akhirnya dua staf ini berhasil menyelesaikan program diklat dengan baik. Sehingga pada saatnya periodisasi pergantian jabatan kepala sekolah nanti, sudah disiapkan pengganti yang akan meneruskan tugas pimpinan di sekolah. Komunikasi dengan berbagai stakeholder, termasuk pimpinan, penting dalam pelayanan, orang tua murid dan sekolah adalah mitra yang bertugas mendampingi prestasi anak. Setiap awal tahun pelajaran, orang tua akan dijelaskan tentang berbagai macam aturan. Selain itu, hal tersebut diwujudkan antara lain dengan mengadakan gathering di bulan Desember setelah satu semester berjalan (lihat Appendix

Foto Sua Ortu), pertemuan dengan orangtua sejatinya adalah untuk terus saling mengawal dan mendukung perkembangan dunia yang perlu diketahui orang tua serta peserta didik agar tidak satu pihak saja (dalam hal ini sekolah) yang dituntut untuk melaksanakan hal tersebut tetapi kedua belah pihak sama-sama terlibat aktif demi perkembangan siswa. Selain itu, dijelaskan pula oleh Kepala Sekolah bahwa ada fasilitas ruang belajar Kosayu yang dapat diakses oleh anak dan orang tua secara digital. Dalam konteks mewujudkan hal tersebut maka berbagai upaya dilakukan secara menyeluruh, termasuk kegiatan kerohanian dan pembekalan untuk guru. Pembinaan rutin juga dilakukan untuk bapak ibu guru bersama dengan pengawas sekolah”

“One of the real examples that most impressed me was the School Principal Candidate Training Program. We sent two leadership staff to this training. This is very important to do, and the results are very effective. When the activity occurs, other staff take over the tasks the training participant staff must leave behind. In the end, these two staff managed to complete the training program well. When the time comes for the period to change the position of the school principal, a replacement will be prepared to continue the leadership duties at the school. Communication with various stakeholders, including leaders, is important in services; parents and schools are partners tasked with assisting children's achievements. At the beginning of each school year, various rules parents are explained. Apart from that, this is realized, among other things, by holding a gathering in December after one semester has been running (Sua Parent Photo Appendix). The purpose of the meeting with parents was to continue monitoring and supporting each other's developments in the world, which parents and students need to know so they don't become one. Only the party (in this case, the school) must implement this, but both parties are actively involved in student development. Apart from that, the Principal also explained that a Kosayu learning room facility can be accessed by children and parents digitally. In realizing this, various efforts were carried out, including spiritual activities and teacher training. Routine coaching was also carried out for teachers together with school supervisors.”

Another example to exemplify management with a heart was a supportive environment to wit:

“Supervisi Tuter Se-Mata Pelajaran. Kegiatan ini rutin dilakukan oleh pimpinan dengan melibatkan semua bapak ibu guru. Guru mengajukan jadwal supervisi. Kemudian pimpinan akan melakukan supervisi bersama satu tutor se mata pelajaran. Sebelum pelaksanaan supervisi dilakukan pra supervisi dengan maksud mengetahui materi yang akan diajarkan, berdiskusi metode yang tepat dan masukan dari pimpinan bersama rekan se mata pelajaran. Setelah supervisi dilakukan kembali umpan balik selama pelaksanaan supervisi. Hal ini sangat efektif karena ada kesempatan saling belajar dan keterbukaan antara pimpinan dan antar guru se mata pelajaran.”

“There is one concrete example that I remember well, namely, Supervision of Speech in All Subjects. This activity is routinely carried out by management involving all teachers. The teacher submits a supervision schedule. Then, the

leader will supervise each subject with one tutor. Before carrying out the supervision, pre-supervision aims to know the material to be taught, discussing appropriate methods and inputs from the leadership with fellow-subjects. After the supervision is carried out, feedback is given again during the implementation of supervision. This is very effective because there is an opportunity for mutual learning and openness between leaders and teachers in all subjects”)

As far as team learning is concerned, strong correlations can also be explained by the response of the school principal. He said that:

“Kita sudah menerapkan implementasi kurikulum merdeka. Evaluasi yang dapat kami sampaikan adalah pelaksanaan dilapangan sangat baik menjawab kebutuhan peserta didik secara personal. Memang semua masih harus terintegrasi dengan sistem pembelajaran di sekolah, akan tetapi jenis mata pelajaran pilihan yang akan dipelajari peserta didik dapat ditentukan oleh peserta didik sendiri dengan persetujuan orangtua dan wali kelas. Tentu saja hal ini benar-benar mewujudkan semangat belajar dengan hati gembira dan tetap bersemangat. Membangun komunitas belajar guru anak dengan harapan terpelajar. Ada tanggung jawab masing-masing antara wali kelas dan orang tua dalam memantau perkembangan siswa”

(“So far, we have implemented the independent curriculum. The evaluation we can convey is that the implementation in the field was very good in responding to students' needs. It is true that everything still has to be integrated with the learning system at school. Still, the types of elective subjects that students will study can be determined by the students themselves with the approval of parents and homeroom teachers. Of course, this embodies the spirit of learning with a happy heart and enthusiasm. We are building a learning community of child teachers with the hope of being educated. The homeroom teacher and parents have respective responsibilities in monitoring student progress”)

Creating mental models because of the school being a learning organization can be supported by the explanation of the school principal:

“Pertama tama dan terutama, kita membangun pemahaman cita cita bersama. Cita-cita kita tertuang dalam profil guru, yaitu “menjadi teladan membentuk insan Kolese Santo Yusup yang saleh dan terpelajar”, saleh saja tidak cukup, mesti terpelajar/berilmu juga. Sebaliknya, terpelajar dan pintar saja tidak cukup, mesti juga berbudi dan saleh. Cita-cita ini selalu disosialisasikan untuk dipahami oleh semua guru dan karyawan. Setelah memahami selanjutnya disediakan wadah untuk mewujudkannya melalui berbagai kegiatan dan workshop/pelatihan, antara lain penyusunan alur pembelajaran yang menuju keberhasilan profil guru, menyusun evaluasi diri guru, dan menyusun pengembangan keprofesian berkelanjutan. Hingga hasilnya akan diukur dengan rubrik ketercapaian profil guru yang diberi penilaian dari peserta didik dan rekan kerja setiap semester. Anda nanti bisa

lihat dan cek melalui RBK (Ruang Belajar Kosayu). RBK muncul karena COVID-19 dan ada informasi bahwa ada tugas yang disampaikan di RBK. RBK sangat penting bagi siswa karena mereka harus mengaksesnya setiap hari untuk bahan pelajaran dan tugas. RBK mencakup segala aspek, termasuk keuangan dan administrasi. Orang tua siswa mungkin bisa mengakses RBK, tetapi belum pasti. Orang tua dapat mengakses informasi melalui RBK agar tidak kelewatan. Beberapa orang tua memiliki kontak yang sulit dihubungi, namun ada efek positif dari perpindahan ke RBK secara formal. Tambahan pula, secara internal, musyawarah MGLP (Musyawarah Guru Lintas Pelajaran) dilakukan setidaknya satu kali dalam sebulan dan selama ini Kepala Sekolah memang tidak terlalu menuntut dokumentasinya, tidak menekankan pentingnya bukti fisik karena bisa diakali/direkayasa. Akan tetapi, berdasar diskusi kali ini, ke depan Kepala Sekolah juga akan memperbaiki tata kelola dokumentasi pengetahuan agar lebih tertib dan bisa dipakai sebagai dasar legacy dan pembelajaran ke masa depan. Menurut beliau, rencana pembelajaran mata pelajaran dilakukan setiap bulan sekali dan harus selalu dikaji ulang. Perlu tenaga khusus dan tidak boleh menyerah dalam pengembangan diri. Komunikasi menjadi faktor penting dalam menyelesaikan kesesuaian permintaan dengan pemberian. Pertemuan informal untuk mengumpulkan informasi kebutuhan. Informasi dapat disampaikan melalui pertemuan kecil secara personal atau rapat formal. Komunikasi informal lebih efektif dalam meningkatkan hubungan antar teman. Pertemuan yang paling akrab adalah saat ada acara atau kegiatan bersama”

“First and foremost, we build an understanding of shared goals. Our ideals are stated in the teacher's profile: "to be a role model in forming people at Santo Yusup College who are pious and educated" Being pious alone is not enough; you must be educated/knowledgeable, too. On the other hand, being educated and smart is not enough; you must also be virtuous and pious. These ideals are always communicated for all teachers and employees to understand. After understanding, a platform is provided to make this happen through various activities and workshops/training, including preparing learning pathways that lead to successful teacher profiles, preparing teacher self-evaluation, and preparing continuous professional development. The results will be measured using a teacher profile achievement rubric assessed by students and colleagues every semester. You can later see and check via RBK (Kosayu Study Room). The RBK emerged because of COVID-19, and there is information that tasks are submitted to the RBK. RBK is very important for students because they must access it daily for study materials and assignments. RBK covers all aspects, including finance and administration. Parents may be able to access the RBK, but it is not certain. Parents can access information through the RBK so they don't miss out. Some parents have difficult contacts, but there are positive effects from moving to RBK formally. Additionally, internally, MGLP (Inter-Subject Teachers' Deliberations) are held at least once a month. So far, the Principal has not been too demanding on documentation, not emphasizing the importance of physical evidence because it can be tricked/engineered. However, based on this discussion, in the future, the Principal will also improve the management of knowledge documentation so that it is more orderly and can be used as a basis for legacy and learning for the future.

According to him, subject learning plans are carried out once every month and must always be reviewed. It requires special energy and must not give up on self-development. Communication is important in completing the match between requests and gifts—informal meetings to gather information on needs. Information can be conveyed through small personal meetings or formal meetings. Informal communication is more effective in improving relationships between friends. The most intimate meetings are when there are events or activities together”)

Finally, the school principal explained the overall learning culture in the organization, both students and teachers and education staff . He shared the initiatives or programs needed to be implemented to improve the organizational learning environment in the future when facing external dynamics. He highlighted the following as depicted in the following excerpts:

“Selama ini, dalam proses kepemimpinan saya bersama para wakil kepala sekolah yang lain, ‘Belajar sepanjang hayat’ adalah semboyan yang tidak akan luntur oleh waktu. Guru adalah teladan, seperti pepatah Jawa: guru..digugu lan ditiru..Maka guru adalah profesi yang selalu berubah mengikuti perkembangan zaman dan kemajuan teknologi serta kebutuhan peserta didik yang juga senantiasa berubah. Sangat diperlukan membangun komunitas dan mau membuka diri, selalu terbuka untuk belajar dari pihak eksternal dan juga menerima pihak yang akan belajar. Cara pandang dan sikap mental ini adalah dasar utama yang menurut saya mesti selalu dikedepankan siapapun nanti yang menjadi kepala sekolah demi kemajuan berkelanjutan dan terus berkembang sekolah ini. Sekolah memiliki visi dan misi untuk menjadi komunitas belajar unggul berpedoman pada standar nasional dan membangun kawula muda menjadi insan yang saleh dan terpelajar, dalam hal ini ditekankan oleh Kepala Sekolah bahwa teladan dari kepala sekolah dan guru sangat penting dalam membentuk siswa menjadi insan yang saleh dan terpelajar, dalam artian bahwa pendidikan harus menggabungkan pengetahuan dan tata krama yang santun, serta mendukung untuk menggelorakan interaksi saling menunggal antar berbagai pemangku kepentingan termasuk orangtua/wali murid. Ada penekanan pada inovasi dan komitmen untuk maju dan belajar. Materi pembelajaran perlu ditingkatkan dengan adanya inovasi dan kreativitas. Inovasi dalam pengembangan sekolah didasari oleh pemahaman akan pentingnya kemajuan sekolah. Inovasi perlu dilakukan untuk melibatkan orang tua atau wali dalam proyek. Selain itu, tenaga kependidikan/karyawan juga berkontribusi. Karyawan harus selektif dan memberikan layanan yang sesuai dengan kebutuhan orang tua dan murid. Ada kegiatan penilaian kinerja untuk perpustakaan dan karyawannya setiap akhir tahun. Ada alokasi waktu dan pelatihan untuk peningkatan kompetensi karyawan. Pengakuan dari masyarakat dan instansi lain merupakan dampak dari upaya yang dilakukan”

("So far, in my leadership process and other vice principals, 'Lifelong learning' is a motto that will not fade with time. Teachers are role models. As the Javanese saying goes, teachers...are admired and imitated...So, teaching is a profession that is always changing, following the times and advances in technology, and the needs of students are also changing. It is necessary to build a community, be willing to open yourself up, always be open to learning from external parties, and accept those who want to know. This perspective and mental attitude is the main basis that, in my opinion, must always be put forward by anyone who becomes a school principal for sustainable progress and continued development of this school. The school has a vision and mission to become a superior learning community guided by national standards and to develop young people into pious and educated people. In this case, the Principal emphasized that the principal's and teachers' examples are very important in shaping students into righteous people. They must be educated in the sense that education must combine knowledge and polite manners, as well as support the promotion of mutually supportive interactions between various stakeholders, including parents/guardians of students. There is an emphasis on innovation and a commitment to progress and learning. Learning materials need to be improved with innovation and creativity. Innovation in school development is based on understanding the importance of school progress. Innovations need to be made to involve parents or guardians in the project. Apart from that, educational staff/employees also contribute. Employees must be selective and provide services that suit the needs of parents and students. There is a performance appraisal activity for the library and its employees at the end of each year. Time allocation and training are needed to increase employee competency. Recognition from the community and other agencies is the impact of the efforts")

In essence, the school principal built a communication system that involves people and a heart that applied humanist leadership—the importance of managing the heart to live the rules. Communication plays an important role in the approach. Seeking solutions to any differences has an impact whenever something might not fit. Communication must be built holistically, including vertical and horizontal.

The responses of the school principal's responses could be interpreted in three major categories:

1. Leadership and Communication Practices:

- Humanist Leadership and Heart-Centered Communication
- Importance of Holistic Communication
- Two-Way Communication

- Shared Goals
- Adaptability and Flexibility
- Collaborative Decision-Making
- Professional Development and Support
- Reflective Practices
- Cultural Awareness and Inclusivity

2. Knowledge Management and Learning Culture:

- Knowledge Transfer and Training
- Supervision and Feedback Loop
- Emphasis on Lifelong Learning
- Innovation and Progress
- Vision of Pious and Educated Individuals

3. Community Engagement and Recognition of Learning Organization:

- Community Involvement and Recognition
- Continuous Professional Development
- Importance of Collaboration
- Student-Centered Approach
- Communication Infrastructure

These interpretations are supported by the following excerpts from the transcript as basis for meaning-making:

1: Humanist Leadership and Heart-Centered Communication

- "So far, in the era of leadership that I have implemented regarding openness and transparency of communication in this school, it has been carried out by building more on heart management."
- "This means that there are regulations that serve as shared guidelines, but in their implementation, they are more humane by building communication that can find solutions and communicating with the heart, not solely by using power as a school leader."

- "The communication process must go both ways, not just one way."

2: Importance of Holistic Communication

- "Communication must be built holistically, including vertical and horizontal."
- "The school principal builds communication that involves people and the heart and applies humanist leadership."

3: Two-Way Communication

- "Two-way communication is well established at SMAK Santo Yusup College because the basis is a culture of building communication with the heart."
- "When the Principal needs a team to complete a special task, the school community will be ready to help."

4: Knowledge Transfer and Training

- "One of the real examples that most impressed me was the School Principal Candidate Training Program."
- "In this training, we sent two leadership staff. This is very important, and the results are very effective."
- "So that when the time comes for the period for changing the position of the school principal, a replacement will have been prepared who will continue the leadership duties at the school."

5: Supervision and Feedback Loop

- "The teacher submits a supervision schedule. Then the leader will supervise each subject with one tutor."
- "After supervision is carried out, feedback is given again during the implementation of supervision."

6: Emphasis on Lifelong Learning

- "'Lifelong learning' is a motto that will not fade with time."

- "Teachers are role models, as the Javanese saying goes: teachers...are admired and imitated..."

7: Innovation and Progress

- "There is an emphasis on innovation and a commitment to progress and learning."
- "Innovations need to be made to involve parents or guardians in the project."

8: Community Involvement and Recognition

- "Recognition from the community and other agencies is the impact of the efforts made."
- "Learning materials need to be improved with innovation and creativity."

9: Vision of Pious and Educated Individuals

- "The school has a vision and mission to become a superior learning community guided by national standards and to develop young people into pious and educated people."
- "In this case, the Principal emphasized that the example of the principal and teachers is very important in shaping students into pious people and educated..."

10: Shared Goals: Emphasizes the importance of aligning individual and organizational goals, fostering a sense of common purpose and direction among staff members.

- "Our ideals are stated in the teacher's profile, namely 'to be a role model in forming people at Santo Yusup College who are pious and educated'."
- "These ideals are always socialized for all teachers and employees to understand."

11: Continuous Professional Development

- "There is time allocation and training to increase employee competency."

12: Importance of Collaboration

- "Apart from that, educational staff/employees also contribute."
- "There is a performance appraisal activity for the library and its employees at the end of each year."

13: Adaptability and Flexibility

- "Teaching is a profession that is always changing following the times and advances in technology, and the needs of students are also always changing."

14: Student-Centered Approach

- "It is true that everything still has to be integrated with the learning system at school, but the types of elective subjects that students will study can be determined by the students themselves with the approval of parents and homeroom teachers."
- "This embodies the spirit of learning with a happy heart and remaining enthusiastic."

15: Collaborative Decision-Making

- "There are respective responsibilities between the homeroom teacher and parents in monitoring student progress."
- "Building a learning community of child teachers with the hope of being educated."

16: Communication Infrastructure

- "RBK is very important for students because they have to access it daily for study materials and assignments."

- "RBK covers all aspects, including finance and administration."

17: Professional Development and Support

- "Internal MGLP (Inter-Subject Teachers' Deliberations) are held at least once a month."
- "The Principal has not been too demanding on documentation, not emphasizing the importance of physical evidence because it can be tricked/engineered."

18: Reflective Practices

- "At the beginning of each school year, various rules are explained to parents."
- "There is time allocation and training to increase employee competency."

19: Cultural Awareness and Inclusivity

- "Always be open to learning from external parties and accept those who want to learn."
- "This perspective and mental attitude is the main basis that, in my opinion, must always be put forward by anyone who becomes a school principal for the sake of sustainable progress and continued development of this school."

Integration of QUAL-QUAN Result Analysis

The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings provides a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between OC, KM, and LO within the school. Table 7 presents a summary of a comprehensive and coherent analysis of OC, KM, and LO based on the quantitative data and qualitative interpretations. The alignment shows the associations of these three variables in explaining how a senior high school operates effectively with communication as lens. Suffice to say that these

associations underscore the assumption that to have a healthy and conducive educational environment, it has to have a an open organizational communication system, where knowledge products are shared and talked about openly to keep tab of emerging changes thereby becoming a learning organization.

Table 5 : Summary Coherence Analysis of OC, KM, and LO

Dimension	Findings	Interpretation
OC (Organizational Communication)	Transparent, two-way communication facilitates knowledge-sharing and feedback loops.	Heart-Centered Communication, Supervision and Feedback Loop
	Clear communication aligns stakeholders with the school's vision and goals.	Themes: Shared Vision, Holistic Communication
KM (Knowledge Management)	Effective communication channels (e.g., regular meetings, internal deliberations).	Themes: Structured Channels, Open Communication
	Regular training and knowledge-sharing sessions ensure continuous learning and skill updates.	Themes: Continuous Professional Development, Collaborative Learning
	KM practices support dynamic and adaptive learning environments.	Themes: Innovation in KM, Reflective Practices
	Accessible KM tools (e.g., RBK) facilitate efficient knowledge dissemination.	Themes: Technological Support, Access to Information
LO (Learning Organization)	Integration of OC and KM enhances adaptability, continuous improvement, and overall effectiveness.	Themes: Adaptability, Continuous Improvement, Unified Goals
	Collaborative learning and interactive engagement promote a culture of continuous improvement.	Themes: Collaborative Learning, Teacher-Student Engagement
	Leadership support and technological infrastructure are critical for sustaining a learning organization.	Themes: Leadership Vision, Technological Infrastructure

Organizational Communication Channels' Contribution to Information Flow, Knowledge Acquisition, and Sharing

This study also aimed to explain how OC channels play a crucial role in shaping information flow, knowledge acquisition, and sharing among different stakeholders in a high school setting. The study showed that effective communication channels within the organization can enhance several aspects, including:

- **Facilitating Information Dissemination:** communication channels such as staff meetings, email correspondence, newsletters, and digital platforms serve as conduits for disseminating important information to stakeholders. School administrators can communicate updates on policies, procedures, curriculum changes, and upcoming events through these channels, ensuring that all school community members are informed.
- **Promoting Knowledge Acquisition:** well-established communication channels provide stakeholders access to educational resources, professional development opportunities, and relevant information. Teachers can leverage these channels to acquire new knowledge, skills, and instructional strategies, enhancing teaching effectiveness and student engagement.
- **Encouraging Collaboration and Sharing:** effective communication channels foster stakeholder collaboration and knowledge-sharing. Teachers can exchange ideas, best practices, and teaching resources through collaborative platforms, staff meetings, and professional learning communities, enriching their collective knowledge base and improving instructional practices.

On the other hand, the school and all stakeholders should be aware of obstruction if they cannot manage and implement it well, the potential barriers to effective communication which includes:

- **Information Overload:** excessive communication or irrelevant information can overwhelm stakeholders, making it difficult to discern important messages and resources. Information overload can hinder knowledge acquisition and sharing by causing confusion, disengagement, and inefficiency.
- **Communication Barriers:** language differences, hierarchical structures, and lack of accessibility can impede effective communication and knowledge exchange. When communication channels are not inclusive or accessible to all stakeholders, certain groups may be marginalized or excluded from important discussions and decision-making processes, limiting the flow of information and knowledge within the school community.
- **Split Communication:** fragmented communication practices can hinder collaboration and knowledge-sharing across different departments or grade levels. Split communication practices may result in duplication of efforts, missed opportunities for synergy, and limited cross-pollination of ideas and perspectives among stakeholders.

Additionally, the results confirm that the rest of the OC variables could expedite KM practices within the context of this senior high school and correspondingly with the interpretations of the interview results which are key aspects of the school principal's responses, encompassing leadership and communication practices, knowledge management initiatives, and the importance of community engagement and recognition within the school context.

Effects of the integration of OC and KM in the development of an LO

The integration of OC and KM significantly impacts the development of an LO. Key findings like the correlation between **VAR1 (Frequency of Communication Channels)** and **VIR4 (Decision-Making Processes)** which showed a moderately strong positive correlation means that the higher the frequency of communication channels in the school environment, the better the decision-making processes in line with the principles of an LO. Effective communication channels provide avenues for sharing information, soliciting feedback, and engaging stakeholders in discussions relevant to decision-making.

Transparency and Decision-Making Effectiveness are meaningfully associated. Specifically, higher levels of openness tended to be associated with more effective decision-making processes. Promoting openness in communication and decision-making processes may lead to better decision outcomes within the senior high school as LO.

Satisfaction with Communication Tools and Shared Vision showed a significant correlation highlights the integral role of communication in fostering a sense of shared purpose and direction within the school. Higher satisfaction levels with communication tools are associated with a greater alignment of goals, values, and objectives among school community members without exception.

Personal Mastery and Communication Tools with positive correlation underscores the pivotal role of communication in promoting collaborative learning environments. Improving communication tools and practices should align with

initiatives to foster personal mastery and knowledge-sharing, ultimately enhancing the school's organizational learning and adaptation capacity in facing the dynamic conditions.

Suffice to say that the study's findings highlighted the critical role of effective organizational communication in facilitating knowledge management practices and fostering a learning organization within the school. Enhanced communication allows for better information flow. Figure 20 is an example where collaboration and feedback exchange among stakeholders occur that led to more informed and timely decision-making.

Figure 20. School information and communication about services

The schools that prioritize and invest in communication strategies to promote dialogue, inclusivity, and information sharing are likely to experience improvements in their decision-making processes. By prioritizing clear, transparent, and inclusive communication strategies, educational leaders can enhance knowledge-sharing, collaboration, and continuous improvement within their institutions. Further research could explore specific mechanisms through which communication influences

knowledge management practices and learning organization development in educational settings.

Role of leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement in OC, KM, and LO

Firstly, **leadership support** is paramount in setting the strategic direction and fostering a conducive environment for effective communication and knowledge-sharing. School leaders serve as catalysts for change, articulating a compelling vision that underscores the importance of transparent communication, collaborative knowledge creation, and continuous improvement. Leaders inspire trust through their unwavering commitment to these principles, engendering a culture of openness and innovation among staff and students.

Based on the key informant interview, the school principal articulated that effective leadership provides a clear vision and direction for the school's communication and knowledge management initiatives. A school leader sets the tone for fostering a culture of open communication, collaboration, and continuous improvement.

Moreover, a leader could allocate financial and human resources to support the implementation of communication and knowledge management strategies. This includes investing in professional development opportunities, technology infrastructure, and staff training programs. School leaders also serve as role models for effective communication and knowledge-sharing behaviors. By demonstrating transparency, accessibility, and a commitment to lifelong learning, they inspire staff and students to participate actively in organizational processes.

Here, there are key strategies to be employed:

- Guiding Vision and Strategy: Leadership is crucial in setting the vision and strategy for OC and KM. The principal's heart-centered leadership at SMAK Kosayu exemplifies how leadership can foster a supportive environment for effective communication and knowledge-sharing.
- Resource Allocation: Leaders prioritizing KM and OC allocate necessary resources, such as training programs and communication platforms, to support these processes.

Technological infrastructure is the backbone of modern educational ecosystems, facilitating seamless communication channels and knowledge dissemination processes. Robust information systems, encompassing digital repositories, learning management platforms, and communication tools, empower stakeholders to access, share, and co-create knowledge resources in real-time. By leveraging technology, the school enhanced the accessibility and scalability of their educational offerings, enriching the learning experience and fostering deeper engagement among learners. Robust technological infrastructure, including digital platforms, databases, and learning management systems, facilitates storing, retrieving, and disseminating knowledge resources. These systems streamline communication channels and enable efficient collaboration among stakeholders.

Technology provides access to many educational resources, such as online libraries, multimedia materials, and virtual learning environments. This enhances the learning experience for students and supports teachers in delivering engaging and interactive lessons. Digital communication tools like email, instant messaging, and video conferencing facilitate real-time communication and collaboration among teachers, administrators, and students. These tools bridge geographical distances and

enable remote learning opportunities. It can be surmised that learning environment should have:

- **Enabling Tools:** Technological tools like Ruang Belajar Kosayu (RBK) facilitate seamless communication and knowledge-sharing, ensuring that information is accessible and learning materials are available to all stakeholders.
- **Innovation and Accessibility:** Technology supports innovative practices and ensures that learning materials are readily available to all stakeholders, fostering a culture of continuous learning and improvement.

Finally, **teacher-student engagement** is central to effective knowledge management and institutional communication practices. As facilitators of learning, teachers play a crucial role in fostering a collaborative learning environment where students are active participants in creating and exchanging knowledge. Through interactive teaching methods such as group discussions, project-based learning and peer-to-peer collaboration, educators empower students to construct meaning, develop critical thinking skills and foster a passion for lifelong learning.

Enthusiastic teachers and students actively participate in creating, sharing and applying knowledge. Teachers encourage student engagement through interactive teaching methods, group discussions and project-based learning activities.

Effective communication channels enable teachers to give timely feedback on student progress, performance and areas for improvement. This fosters a learning environment where students feel valued and motivated to learn for themselves. Teachers facilitate collaborative learning where students work together to solve

problems, exchange ideas and construct meaning. This encourages knowledge-sharing among peers and develops critical thinking, communication and teamwork skills. These could be further explained by having:

- Interactive Learning: Effective OC and KM practices promote interactive learning environments where teachers and students actively engage with each other. This engagement is crucial for developing a learning organization, ensuring that knowledge is transmitted, discussed, critiqued, and expanded upon.
- Building Relationships: Strong communication channels help build trust and rapport between teachers and students. Themes from the thematic analysis, such as "Holistic Communication," emphasize the importance of these relationships in creating a supportive and nurturing learning environment.

In short, the synergistic interplay of leadership support, technological infrastructure and teacher-student engagement (Figure 21 as practice of this engagement) forms the cornerstone of effective institutional communication and knowledge management in secondary school. By fostering a culture of collaboration, innovation and student-centred learning, these elements guide the school towards developing a dynamic, adaptive and flexible learning organization that enables students to thrive in an evolving world.

Figure 21. *Learning Processes with Engagement*

Integrating OC and KM is fundamental to developing the school as an LO. It enhances adaptability by ensuring quick and effective communication and continuous knowledge updating. It supports continuous improvement through regular feedback and collaborative learning and boosts overall effectiveness by aligning stakeholders and enabling informed decision-making. Leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement are critical mediating factors that ensure the successful integration of OC and KM practices, ultimately fostering an environment where continuous learning and improvement thrive.

By leveraging these integrated practices, the senior high school in Malang, Indonesia, can develop into a robust learning organization capable of adapting to changes, continuously improving their practices, and achieving their educational goals more effectively. Leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement are key elements that mediate the relationship between institutional

communication, knowledge management, and learning organization development. Fostering a culture of collaboration, innovation and continuous improvement, these elements create a dynamic, student-centered learning environment that prepares students for success in the 21st century (Figure 22).

Figure 22. *One moment of student-centered learning environment*

Based on the results of statistical analyses and qualitative responses, it is quite interesting and challenging to observe and study the associations of these three variables further in the future. In a case study, it is common that the range of implications may be limited and cannot be directly considered to represent or draw conclusions from that are general and applicable in all organizational situations and conditions, hence, results are not generalizable to all high school settings. However, it can offer a glimpse on the plausibility of findings as experienced by St Josef High School in Malang, Indonesia.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study explored the interrelationships or associations between OC, KM, and LO within St. Josef Senior High School in Malang, Indonesia. Using a mixed methods approach, the study aimed to determine the current organizational communication practices in a senior high school in Malang, Indonesia that facilitate or hinder effective knowledge management practices, explain how organizational communication channels contribute to or impede the flow of information, knowledge acquisition, and sharing among stakeholders in a high school setting; examine the effects of the integration of organizational communication and knowledge management in the development of a learning organization like St Josef High School; and analyze the role of leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement in mediating the relationship between organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization in St. Josef High School.

This mixed methods approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of how OC, KM, and LO interact within an educational institution. The quantitative analysis quantified the strengths and directions of association among variables, while the qualitative analysis provided context and depth, uncovering the lived experiences that underpinned these relationships. The integration of these two methods enhanced the validity and richness of the findings, making this analysis particularly valuable for academic research. By exploring how communication and knowledge management practices impact the development of a learning organization in a specific high school,

it examined the relationship between organizational communication and knowledge management processes in this educational institution, exploring how these practices promote adaptability, continuous improvement, and knowledge dissemination for sustained growth, especially in the context of the VUCA (Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, and Ambiguous) educational landscape.

Of the 75 hypotheses tested, 38 showed either strong or moderate positive correlations. Results showed that all KM and LO variables were positively correlated which established the associations of specific KM variables such as knowledge accessibility, knowledge transfer and training, knowledge management practices, knowledge documentation, and knowledge-sharing practices with LO variables like shared vision, personal mastery, team learning, decision-making, and mental models. In effect, it can be said that KM creates LO. KM is like a bridge that teachers and staff should pass to become an LO.

Suffice to say that associations of variables with positive correlations among OC, KM, and LO are determinants that the school had put in place to ensure a relevant and responsive educational institution. These are frequency of using communication channels with sharing practices; transparency and knowledge accessibility; KM practices and satisfaction of communication tools used; satisfaction with communication tools use and knowledge-sharing practices; communication clarity and knowledge accessibility; communication clarity and knowledge documentation; communication clarity and knowledge sharing; two-way communication and KM practices.

The qualitative responses from the key informant interviewee corroborated these associations of variables that led to the following interpretations that shaped the

existing associations of OC, KM, and LO such as: Humanist Leadership and Heart-Centered Communication, Importance of Holistic Communication, Two-Way Communication, Knowledge Transfer and Training; Supervision and Feedback Loop; Emphasis on Lifelong Learning; Innovation and Progress; Community Involvement and Recognition; Vision of Pious and Educated Individuals; Shared Goals; Continuous Professional Development; Importance of Collaboration; Adaptability and Flexibility; Student-Centered Approach; Collaborative Decision-Making; Communication Infrastructure; Professional Development and Support; and Reflective Practices; and Cultural Awareness and Inclusivity.

This study also aimed to explain how OC channels played a crucial role in shaping information flow, knowledge acquisition, and sharing among different stakeholders in a high school setting. OC facilitated information dissemination; promoted knowledge acquisition; and encouraged collaboration and sharing. However, too much information can lead to information overload; communication barriers; and split communication.

The effects of the integration of OC and KM in the development of an LO led to better decision-making processes due to transparent communication; satisfaction with communication tools and shared vision; personal mastery and online communication tools provided.

The role of leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement in OC, KM, and LO also featured greatly in the school. Based on the key informant interview, the school principal articulated that effective leadership provides a clear vision and direction for the school's communication and knowledge management initiatives. A school leader sets the tone for fostering a culture of open

communication, collaboration, and continuous improvement. The key strategies include: Guiding Vision and Strategy; Resource Allocation; Technological infrastructure; and teacher-student engagement.

In short, the synergistic interplay of leadership support, technological infrastructure and teacher-student engagement forms the cornerstone of effective institutional communication and knowledge management in secondary school. By fostering a culture of collaboration, innovation and student-centred learning, these elements guide the school towards developing a dynamic, adaptive and flexible learning organization that enables students to thrive in an evolving world.

Based on the results of statistical analyses and qualitative responses, it is quite interesting and challenging to observe and study the associations of these three variables further in the future. In a case study, it is common that the range of implications may be limited and cannot be directly considered to represent or draw conclusions from that are general and applicable in all organizational situations and conditions, hence, results are not generalizable to all high school settings. However, it can offer a glimpse on the plausibility of findings as experienced by St Josef High School in Malang, Indonesia.

Conclusions

The study attempted to determine the current organizational communication practices in a senior high school in Malang, Indonesia that facilitate or hinder effective knowledge management practices, explain how organizational communication channels contribute to or impede the flow of information, knowledge acquisition, and sharing among stakeholders in a high school setting; examine the effects of the

integration of organizational communication and knowledge management in the development of a learning organization like St Josef High School; and analyze the role of leadership support, technological infrastructure, and teacher-student engagement in mediating the relationship between organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization in St. Josef High School.

OC as a foundation revealed that effective communication is fundamental to the success of KM and the development of LO. Strong correlations were found between OC and both KM and LO, highlighting the importance of transparent, two-way communication in fostering knowledge sharing and organizational learning. The interdependence of KM and LO indicates that effective KM practices are crucial for sustaining a learning organization. Qualitative insights supported this by emphasizing the school's commitment to collaborative learning and practical knowledge management.

Challenges in knowledge documentation: while the school excelled in many areas, the qualitative analysis revealed challenges in formalizing knowledge documentation. Despite the absence of a formal system, the school's emphasis on process-oriented knowledge sharing suggests a dynamic approach that could benefit from more structured documentation practices.

The leadership's role in fostering a learning culture could be attributed to the school principal's human-centered leadership style in creating a supportive environment for both KM and LO. The emphasis on empathy, inclusivity, and strategic communication aligns with the quantitative findings, underscoring the importance of leadership in integrating these practices.

The key findings underscore the importance of integrating OC, KM, and LO practices to create a cohesive, adaptive, and innovative organizational environment. By addressing the identified challenges, particularly in knowledge documentation, and building on its strengths in communication and collaboration, the school can enhance its capacity to sustain long-term success as a learning organization. Effective communication serves as the foundation for both KM and LO, with leadership playing a critical role in fostering a learning culture.

This integrated analysis does not only contribute to the theoretical understanding of these constructs but also offers practical guidance for educational institutions seeking to navigate the complexities of organizational development in an ever-changing educational landscape.

Recommendations

For further research:

1. Future research could explore the integration of artificial intelligence in communication platforms and conduct longitudinal studies to track the long-term impact of specific communication interventions on organizational culture, investigating how AI-driven tools can enhance communication efficiency and contribute to the cultural evolution of high schools.
2. Longitudinal studies tracking the long-term impact of specific communication interventions on organizational culture would provide valuable insights. The evolving landscape of digital communication, the role of leadership, and the

influence of cultural dimensions collectively shape the communication-cultural nexus within educational institutions.

3. Looking ahead, trends such as integrating emerging technologies, a deeper understanding of neuroscientific principles in learning, and a focus on organizational resilience and agility are anticipated to shape the future of learning organizations.

For practical applications:

4. **Enhancing knowledge documentation** by developing formalized systems for capturing and storing knowledge could strengthen KM practices.
5. **Promoting collaborative learning** by expanding peer learning and interdisciplinary collaboration could further enhance knowledge sharing and innovation.
6. **Continue investing in communication infrastructure** as tools and training users is crucial for supporting KM and LO.

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APPENDIX A
QUESTIONNAIRE

	Pertanyaan Kuesioner	Question (translation)	Variable name
OC /VAR1	<p>Berdasarkan pengalaman Anda selama ini, seberapa sering Anda berpartisipasi dalam rapat rutin staf di mana informasi penting disampaikan/dikomunikasikan?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Tidak pernah Jarang Kadang ikut kadang tidak Sering Selalu</p>	<p>Based on your experience, how often do you participate in regular staff meetings where important information is conveyed/communicated?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Never Seldom Sometimes yes, sometimes no Frequently Always</p>	Frequency of Communication Channels
VAR2	<p>Sejauh mana Anda merasa cukup mendapat informasi tentang keputusan dan/atau perubahan penting yang diberlakukan sekolah?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Tidak pernah diberitahu Jarang diberitahu langsung diberlakukan Kadang diberitahu kadang tidak Sering diberitahu Selalu diberitahu</p>	<p>To what extent do you feel well-informed about important decisions and or changes the school is implementing?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Never Seldom Sometimes yes, sometimes no Frequently Always</p>	Transparency
VAR3	<p>Seberapa puaskah Anda dengan penggunaan aplikasi berbasis online (misalnya RBK, Ruang Belajar Kosayu) untuk melakukan komunikasi di sekolah selama ini?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Sangat tidak puas Tidak puas Cukup puas Puas Sangat puas</p>	<p>How satisfied are you with using online-based applications (e.g., RBK=Ruang Belajar Kosayu, Kosayu Study Room, its online management system for communicating) in school communication so far?</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Very not satisfy Not satisfy Enough Satisfy Very satisfy</p>	Satisfaction with Communication Tools

VAR4	<p>Menurut pendapat Anda, apakah proses komunikasi di sekolah selama ini telah bebas dari ambiguitas dan kesalahpahaman?</p> <p>Selalu terjadi kesalahpahaman dan ambigu Masih sering terjadi kesalahpahaman dan ambigu Kadang kadang terjadi Sebagian besar telah tidak ada kesalahpahaman dan ambigu Telah bebas dari ambiguitas dan kesalahpahaman</p>	<p>In your opinion, has the communication process in school been free from ambiguity and misunderstanding?</p> <p>Always ambiguous Frequently ambiguous Sometimes ambiguous Almost no ambiguity anymore Never misunderstanding and ambiguous</p>	Communication Clarity
VAR 5	<p>Sejauh mana Anda yakin bahwa pendapat dan saran Anda dihargai dan dipertimbangkan dalam proses pengambilan keputusan di sekolah?</p> <p>Sangat tidak yakin Tidak yakin Ragu-ragu Yakin Sangat yakin</p>	<p>To what extent do you believe your opinions and suggestions are valued and considered in the school's decision-making process?</p> <p>Very not sure Not sure Doubt Sure Very sure</p>	Two-Way Communication
KM/ VER1	<p>Menurut pendapat Anda, seberapa cepat para guru/ staf dapat mengakses informasi atau pengetahuan yang mereka perlukan untuk menjalankan peran/tugas mereka secara efektif?</p> <p>Sangat lambat Lambat Kurang cepat Cepat Sangat cepat</p>	<p>How quickly can teachers/staff access the information or knowledge they need to carry out their roles/duties effectively?</p> <p>Very slow Slow Sometimes not fast Fast Very fast</p>	Knowledge Accessibility
VER2	<p>Seberapa sering pelatihan, seminar, lokakarya dan bentuk lainnya diselenggarakan sekolah agar terjadi transfer pengetahuan dan keterampilan</p>	<p>How often are training, seminars, workshops and other forms held by the school to ensure the transfer of knowledge and</p>	Knowledge Transfer and Training

	<p>bagi para guru dan/atau tenaga kependidikan?</p> <p>Tidak pernah Jarang Cukup sering Sering Selalu ada tiap minggu</p>	<p>skills to teachers and or education staff?</p> <p>Never Seldom Not sure Frequently Always every week</p>	
VER3	<p>Menurut Anda, sejauh mana platform digital dan teknologi digital dimanfaatkan untuk pengelolaan pengetahuan di sekolah?</p> <p>Sangat kurang dimanfaatkan/digunakan Kurang dimanfaatkan/digunakan Cukup dimanfaatkan/digunakan Banyak dimanfaatkan/digunakan Sangat banyak dimanfaatkan/digunakan</p>	<p>To what extent are digital platforms and technology used for school knowledge management?</p> <p>Very underused Underused Enough to use Widely used Very widely used</p>	Knowledge Management Practices
VER4	<p>Berdasar pengalaman Anda selama ini, setujukah bahwa berbagai program transfer pengetahuan dan pelatihan di sekolah ini telah didokumentasikan dan disimpan secara efektif dalam memfasilitasi pertukaran dan perolehan informasi dan keahlian di antara para pendidik dan/atau tenaga kependidikan di masa mendatang?</p> <p>Sangat tidak setuju Tidak setuju Netral Setuju Sangat setuju</p>	<p>Based on your experience, do you agree that various knowledge transfer and training programs at this school have been documented and stored effectively to facilitate change and acquisition of information and expertise among educators and or edu/</p> <p>Really not agree Not agree Neutral Agree Really agree</p>	Knowledge documentation
VER5	<p>Menurut pengalaman Anda, seberapa sering Anda terlibat dalam berbagi pengetahuan</p>	<p>In your experience, how often do you share knowledge and insights</p>	The knowledge-sharing practices

	<p>dan wawasan dengan rekan-rekan kerja Anda di sekolah?</p> <p>Tidak pernah Jarang sekali Sesekali saja pernah Sering selalu</p>	<p>with your colleagues at school?</p> <p>Never Seldom Sometimes Frequently Always</p>	
LO/ VIR1	<p>Seberapa yakin Anda bahwa visi dan tujuan sekolah dikomunikasikan dan dipahami oleh seluruh tenaga pendidik dan/atau tenaga kependidikan di sekolah ini?</p> <p>Sangat tidak yakin Tidak yakin Ragu ragu Yakin Sangat yakin</p>	<p>How confident are you that the school's vision and goals are communicated and understood by all teaching and or educational staff at this school?</p> <p>Really not sure Not sure Doubtful Certain Very certain</p>	Shared Vision
VIR2	<p>"Saya merasa bahwa saya terus meningkatkan dan menguasai keterampilan baru di sekolah ini bagi perkembangan pribadi dan peserta didik."</p> <p>Sangat tidak setuju Tidak setuju Netral Setuju Sangat setuju</p>	<p>"I feel that I am constantly improving and mastering new skills at this school for personal and student development."</p> <p>Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree</p>	Personal Mastery
VIR3	<p>Seberapa seringkah Anda berkolaborasi dengan pendidik lain atau tenaga kependidikan lain untuk mengembangkan strategi memecahkan tantangan pengajaran dan/atau pelayanan kepada peserta didik?</p> <p>Tidak pernah Jarang Cukup sering Sering</p>	<p>How often do you collaborate with other educators or educational personnel to develop strategies for solving teaching and/or service student challenges?</p> <p>Never Seldom Sometimes Frequently</p>	Team Learning

	selalu	Always	
VIR4	<p>Selama ini, seberapa terlibat/dilibatkan Anda dalam proses pengambilan keputusan di sekolah?</p> <p>Tidak pernah Jarang terlibat/dilibatkan Cukup terlibat/dilibatkan Sering terlibat/dilibatkan Selalu terlibat/dilibatkan</p>	<p>During this time, how involved/involved are you in the decision-making process at school?</p> <p>Never Seldom Sometimes Frequently Always</p>	<p>Systems Thinking, c.q. Decision Making</p>
VIR5	<p>Sejauh mana Anda yakin bahwa asumsi pribadi Anda tentang pembelajaran yang Anda ampu atau tugas yang Anda jalankan akan memengaruhi tindakan dan keputusan Anda di lingkungan sekolah?</p> <p>Sangat tidak yakin Tidak yakin Ragu ragu Yakin Sangat yakin</p>	<p>To what extent do you believe your assumptions about the learning you teach or the tasks you undertake will influence your actions and decisions in the school environment?</p> <p>Very unsure Not sure Doubtful Sure Strongly sure</p>	<p>Mental Models</p>

APPENDIX B

Interview Guide

This semi-structured interview guide is designed to elicit comprehensive information and expert opinions from key informants regarding organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization principles within senior high school. Interviewers can use probing questions to further explore specific areas of interest based on the key informant's expertise and responses. Interviewing for qualitative investigation entails accuracy and confidentiality and can yield better results depending on the investigator's knowledge. Researchers should know that the key to semi-structured interviews is to maintain flexibility. In contrast, researchers have predetermined questions open to exploring unexpected insights that participants may bring up during the conversation.

Below is a semi-structured interview guide tailored for key informants who hold significant knowledge and expertise related to organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization principles within the senior high school:

Introduction:

1. Thank you, and I appreciate the key informant for participating in the interview. Greet the participant warmly.
2. Briefly introduce the researcher self and explain the purpose of the interview: to gather insights and expertise on organizational communication, knowledge management, and learning organization principles within the senior high school to develop the doctoral dissertation. Briefly explain the purpose of the interview and its importance to the research.
3. Assure confidentiality and explain how the information will only be used for research purposes.

Background and Expertise:

Please provide some background information about your role and experience within the education sector, particularly in this senior high school (Kosayu).

Organizational Communication:

6. How would you characterize the state of organizational communication within senior high school?
7. In your experience, what does senior high school employ some effective communication strategies to facilitate collaboration and information sharing among staff, students, and administrators?
8. Can you discuss any challenges or barriers to effective communication within the school environment and how they are addressed?

Knowledge Management:

9. From your perspective, how do senior high schools document and manage knowledge related to teaching methodologies, curriculum development, and best practices?
10. How does technology facilitate knowledge-sharing and storage within senior high school?

11. Have you observed or been involved in successful knowledge management initiatives or programs within senior high school?
12. How do senior high schools ensure that knowledge is accessible and utilized effectively by teachers and administrators?

Learning Organization Principles:

13. How would you assess the extent to which senior high school embody the principles of a learning organization?
14. Can you discuss any shared vision or goals that guide senior high school efforts toward organizational learning?
15. What are some effective strategies for promoting personal mastery and continuous learning among staff members?
16. How do senior high schools foster team learning and collaboration among teaching teams?
17. Can you provide examples of how senior high schools challenge and address existing mental models or assumptions about teaching and learning?
18. How are decision-making processes structured to support organizational learning and adaptability within senior high school?

Conclusion and Closing:

Do you want to add anything else about organizational communication, knowledge management, or learning organization principles within senior high school?
Thank the key informant for their valuable insights and express gratitude for their time and useful insights.

APPENDIX C

Thematic Analysis Process and Output

The goal of this thematic analysis is to uncover the underlying themes that emerge from the Principal's responses and to interpret their implications within the context of the research. For this coding process, the researcher used the initials such as R = researcher and SP = School Principal as the Key Informant.

The table below shows that this is taken from a real interview conducted with the school principal as part of a study that explored perspectives on the research topic. The extract covers about 65 minutes of the interview. After being familiar with that qualitative data (the interview transcript), the researcher tries to identify the sub-themes and themes by recognizing the keywords of the SP's responses

TRANSCRIPTION	TRANSLATION	KEYWORDS	CODES*)	THEMES
<p>Researcher (R): terima kasih atas waktunya pak. Diskusi kita hari ini pertama akan focus pada aspek TRANSPARANSI KOMUNIKASI yang mengacu pada kejelasan dan keterbukaan komunikasi yang jelas dan terbuka dalam seluruh jajaran dan lingkup kerja di SMAK KOSAYU. Tolong Bapak jelaskan, bagaimana selama Anda memimpin dalam menerapkan transparansi komunikasi tersebut selama ini?</p>	<p>R: Thank you for your time, Sir. Our discussion today will first focus on the COMMUNICATION TRANSPARENCY aspect, which refers to the clarity and openness of clear and open communication at all levels and in the scope of work at SMAK KOSAYU. Please explain how you have led the way in implementing communication transparency so far.</p>			
<p>School Principal (SP): Sejauh ini, di era kepemimpinan yang saya terapkan terkait keterbukaan dan</p>	<p>SP: So far, in the era of leadership that I have implemented regarding openness and transparency of</p>	<p>Leadership Openness Transparency</p>	<p>Lead Transparency</p>	<p>Organizational</p>

<p>transparansi komunikasi di sekolah ini dilakukan dengan lebih membangun pada pengelolaan hati. Artinya ada peraturan yang dijadikan sebagai pedoman bersama, tetapi pada pelaksanaannya lebih humanis dengan membangun komunikasi yang dapat menemukan solusi serta komunikasi dengan hati tidak semata-mata dengan menggunakan kekuasaan sebagai pimpinan sekolah. Jadi proses komunikasi harus berjalan dua arah tidak satu arah saja.</p> <p>Kepala sekolah membangun komunikasi yang melibatkan orang dan hati serta menerapkan kepemimpinan yang humanis, Pentingnya mengelola hati untuk taat kepada peraturan. Komunikasi memainkan peran penting dalam pendekatan. Mencari solusi dari setiap perbedaan berdampak setiap kali ada sesuatu yang mungkin tidak pas. Komunikasi harus dibangun secara menyeluruh, termasuk yang vertikal dan horizontal.</p>	<p>communication in this school, it has been carried out by building more on heart management. This means that there are regulations that serve as shared guidelines. Still, they are more humane in their implementation by creating communication that can find solutions and communicate with the heart, not solely by using power as a school leader. So, the communication process must go both ways, not just one way.</p> <p>The school principal builds communication that involves people and the heart and applies humanist leadership—the importance of managing the heart to obey the rules. Communication plays an important role in the approach. Seeking solutions to any differences has an impact whenever something might not fit. Communication must be built holistically, including vertical and horizontal.</p>	<p>Two-way communication</p> <p>Heart mgmt. Humane Communicating with heart</p> <p>Both ways comm.</p>	<p>Communication Clarity and Lead</p> <p>Two-Way Communication</p>	<p>Communication (with Leadership factor)</p>
<p>R:Selanjutnya, terkait proses komunikasi dua arah. Selama kepemimpinan Bapak, tolong dipaparkan sejauh mana komunikasi dua</p>	<p>R: Next, related to the two-way communication process. During your leadership, please explain how two-way communication at</p>			

<p>arah di sekolah KOSAYU telah berjalan baik dan bagaimana cara keseharian Bapak menerapkan hal tersebut? Bisa tolong diberi 1 contoh nyata.</p>	<p>KOSAYU school has gone well and how you implement this daily. Can you please give one real example?</p>			
<p>SP: Komunikasi dua arah pasti terbangun dengan baik di SMAK Kolese Santo Yusup, karena dasarnya memang budaya membangun komunikasi dengan hati. Ketika Kepala Sekolah memerlukan tim untuk menyelesaikan tugas khusus, warga sekolah akan siap membantu. Sebaliknya, ketika warga sekolah memerlukan kebijakan khusus, Kepala Sekolah siap mendengarkan dan mencari solusi. Contoh: 1. Ketika sekolah memiliki pekerjaan khusus kepanitiaan dalam even tertentu, maka tim yang dimintai tolong akan mempersiapkan sebaik mungkin tanpa mempermasalahkan jam kerja. Terkadang harus melanjutkan pekerjaan itu meskipun melebihi jam kerja yang telah disepakati. Ketika karyawan memiliki kepentingan keluarga, maka Kepala Sekolah memberikan izin khusus meskipun melewati ketentuan peraturan. Dan dapat dipastikan guru lain tetap berkenan untuk menggantikan tugas</p>	<p>SP: Two-way communication is well established at SMAK Santo Yusup College because the basis is a culture of building communication with the heart. When the Principal needs a team to complete a special task, the school community will be ready to help. On the other hand, when the school community needs a special policy, the Principal is prepared to listen and find a solution. Example: 1. When a school has special committee work for a certain event, the team that is asked for help will prepare as best as possible without worrying about working hours. Sometimes, you must continue the work despite exceeding the agreed working hours. When employees have family interests, the Principal gives special permission even though it violates regulatory requirements. You can also be sure that other teachers will still be willing to take over the teaching duties that the teacher has to leave. This information is intended to provide an</p>	<p>Culture of building comm. With heart</p>	<p>Frequency of Communication Channels Transparency Satisfaction with Communication Tools Communication Clarity Two-Way Communication</p>	<p>Organizational Communication</p>

<p>mengajar yang harus ditinggalkan guru tersebut.</p> <p>Tujuan dari menyampaikan informasi tersebut adalah untuk memberikan gambaran kepada pihak luar, seperti orang tua siswa yang ingin menyekolahkan anaknya di sekolah tersebut.</p>	<p>overview to outside parties, such as parents of students who want to send their children to that school.</p>			
<p>R: Sebelumnya sempat disinggung telah banyak program/kegiatan transfer pengetahuan dan pelatihan di sekolah guna mendorong dan memfasilitasi pertukaran, pengetahuan, keterampilan dan keahlian di antara anggota staf. Tolong jelaskan 1 event diantara sekian banyak kegiatan/program tersebut yang menurut Bapak paling berhasil dan paling penting maknaya bagi kemajuan sekolah dan para peserta didik?</p>	<p>R: Previously, it was mentioned that there are many knowledge transfer and training programs/activities in school to encourage and facilitate the exchange of knowledge, skills and expertise between staff members. Please explain one event among the many activities/programs that you think is the most successful and important for the progress of the school and the students.</p>			
<p>SP: Program Diklat Calon Kepala Sekolah. Dalam diklat ini kami megirimkan dua staf pimpinan. Hal ini sangat penting dikerjakan dan hasilnya sangat efektif. Ketika kegiatan berlangsung staf yang lain mengambil alih tugas yang harus ditinggalkan oleh staf peserta diklat. Hingga akhirnya dua staf ini berhasil menyelesaikan program diklat dengan baik. Sehingga pada saatnya periodisasi pergantian jabatan kepala sekolah nanti, sudah disiapkan pengganti yang</p>	<p>SP: One of the real examples that most impressed me was the School Principal Candidate Training Program. We sent two leadership staff to this training. This is very important to do, and the results are very effective. When the activity occurs, other staff take over the tasks the training participant staff must leave behind. In the end, these two staff managed to complete the training program well. When the time comes for the period to change the position of</p>	<p>Leadership programme</p> <p>Continuity of leadership and improveme nt</p> <p>Communica tion with various</p>	<p>Continuous improvement</p>	<p>Leadership factor</p> <p>Learning Organizati on principles</p>

<p>akan meneruskan tugas pimpinan di sekolah.</p> <p>Komunikasi dengan berbagai stakeholder, termasuk pimpinan, penting dalam pelayanan, orang tua murid dan sekolah adalah mitra yang bertugas mendampingi prestasi anak. Setiap awal tahun pelajaran, orang tua akan dijelaskan tentang berbagai macam aturan. Selain itu, hal tersebut diwujudkan antara lain dengan mengadakan gathering di bulan Desember setelah satu semester berjalan (lihat Appendix Foto Sua Ortu), pertemuan dengan orangtua sejatinya adalah untuk terus saling mengawal dan mendukung perkembangan dunia yang perlu diketahui orang tua serta peserta didik agar tidak satu pihak saja (dalam hal ini sekolah) yang dituntut untuk melaksanakan hal tersebut tetapi kedua belah pihak sama-sama terlibat aktif demi perkembangan siswa. Selain itu, dijelaskan pula oleh Kepala Sekolah bahwa ada fasilitas ruang belajar Kosayu yang dapat diakses oleh anak dan orang tua secara digital.</p> <p>Dalam konteks mewujudkan hal tersebut maka berbagai upaya dilakukan secara menyeluruh, termasuk</p>	<p>the school principal, a replacement will be prepared to continue the leadership duties at the school.</p> <p>Communication with various stakeholders, including leaders, is important in services; parents and schools are partners tasked with assisting children's achievements. At the beginning of each school year, parents will be explained about various rules. Apart from that, this is realized, among other things, by holding a gathering in December after one semester has been running (see Sua Parent Photo Appendix). The purpose of meeting with parents is to continue monitoring and supporting each other's developments in the world, which parents and students need to know so they don't become one. Only the party (in this case, the school) must implement this, but both parties are actively involved in student development. Apart from that, the Principal also explained that a Kosayu learning room facility can be accessed by children and parents digitally.</p> <p>In realizing this, various efforts were carried out, including spiritual activities and teacher training. Routine coaching is also carried out for</p>	<p>stakeholders</p> <p>Parents and school are partners.</p> <p>Parents meet every semester.</p> <p>RBK (Ruang Belajar Kosayu, one of comm. Channel)</p> <p>Training for teachers, coaching, also</p>	<p>Knowledge-sharing</p> <p>Knowledge transfer and training</p>	<p>Knowledge Management</p>
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<p>kegiatan kerohanian dan pembekalan untuk guru. Pembinaan rutin juga dilakukan untuk bapak ibu guru bersama dengan pengawas sekolah.</p>	<p>teachers together with school supervisors.</p>			
<p>R: lebih lanjut, tolong paparkan contoh keberhasilan praktek dan inisiatif berbagi pengetahuan/informasi (Knowledge-sharing) diantara para Pendidikan maupun tenaga kependidikan yang terjadi selama ini? Tolong dijelaskan juga 1 contoh nyata yang bisa diamati dalam keseharian.</p>	<p>R: Please explain examples of successful practices and initiatives to share knowledge/information (Knowledge-sharing) between education and educational staff that have occurred so far. Please also explain one real example that can be observed in everyday life.</p>			
<p>SP: Supervisi Tutor Se-Mata Pelajaran Kegiatan ini rutin dilakukan oleh pimpinan dengan melibatkan semua bapak ibu guru. Guru mengajukan jadwal supervisi. Kemudian pimpinan akan melakukan supervisi bersama satu tutor se mata pelajaran. Sebelum pelaksanaan supervisi dilakukan pra supervisi dengan maksud mengetahui materi yang akan diajarkan , berdiskusi metode yang tepat dan masukan dari pimpinan bersama rekan se mata pelajaran. Setelah supervisi dilakukan kembali umpan balik selama pelaksanaan supervisi. Hal ini sangat efektif karena ada kesempatan saling belajar dan keterbukaan antara</p>	<p>SP: There is one concrete example that I remember well, namely Supervision of Speech in All Subjects This activity is routinely carried out by the leadership involving all teachers. The teacher submits a supervision schedule. Then, the leader will supervise each subject with one tutor. Before carrying out supervision, pre-supervision aims to know the material to be taught, discussing appropriate methods and input from the leadership with fellow-subjects. After supervision is carried out, feedback is given again during the implementation of supervision. This is very effective because there is an opportunity for mutual learning and openness</p>	<p>Supervision of Speech in all Subjects</p> <p>Feedback after supervision</p> <p>Mutual learning and openness between leaders and teachers in all subjects</p>	<p>The feedback loop in learning organization practices</p> <p>Shared vision and team learning</p>	<p>Learning Organization</p>

pimpinan dan antar guru se mata pelajaran.	between leaders and teachers in all subjects.			
R: Kegiatan pembelajaran kolektif dalam tim pengajar di sekolah KOSAYU, baik berbasis K13 maupun Kurikulum Merdeka, telah sering dilakukan. Tolong Bapak beri evaluasi seberapa efektif proses tersebut dalam meningkatkan praktik pengajaran dan hasil siswa/prestasi peserta didik secara umum.	R: Collective learning activities within the teaching team at KOSAYU school, both based on K13 and the Merdeka Curriculum, have been carried out frequently. Please evaluate how effective the process is in improving teaching practices and student outcomes/student achievement in general.			
SP: Kita sudah menerapkan implementasi kurikulum merdeka. Evaluasi yang dapat kami sampaikan adalah pelaksanaan dilapangan sangat baik menjawab kebutuhan peserta didik secara personal. Memang semua masih harus terintegrasi dengan sistem pembelajaran di sekolah, akan tetapi jenis mata pelajaran pilihan yang akan dipelajari peserta didik dapat ditentukan oleh peserta didik sendiri dengan persetujuan orangtua dan wali kelas. Tentu saja hal ini benar-benar mewujudkan semangat belajar dengan hati gembira dan tetap bersemangat. Membangun komunitas belajar guru anak dengan harapan terpelajar. Ada tanggung jawab masing-masing antara	SP: So far, we have implemented the independent curriculum. The evaluation we can convey is that the implementation in the field was very good in responding to students' needs. It is true that everything still has to be integrated with the learning system at school. Still, the types of elective subjects that students will study can be determined by the students themselves with the approval of parents and homeroom teachers. Of course, this embodies the spirit of learning with a happy heart and enthusiasm. We are building a learning community of child teachers with the hope of being educated. The homeroom teacher and parents have respective responsibilities	<p>Curriculum evaluation of its implementation</p> <p>The spirit of learning with a happy heart and remaining enthusiastic</p> <p>Building learning community</p> <p>Respective responsibilities between</p>	<p>Mental model</p> <p>Knowledge-sharing</p> <p>Team learning</p>	<p>Learning Organization</p> <p>Knowledge Management</p>

wali kelas dan orang tua dalam memantau perkembangan siswa.	in monitoring student progress.	teachers and parents		
R: Dalam konteks Learning Organization/Organisasi Pembelajar, Tolong Bapak jelaskan, selama Anda memimpin seluruh kawan-kawan SMAK KOSAYU, 1 pengalaman konkrit mengenai perubahan mental model dari para pendidik dan tenaga kependidikan yang berdampak positif pada situasi kerja dan kemajuan sekolah?	R: In the context of a Learning Organization/Learning Organization, During your time leading all SMAK KOSAYU friends, please explain one concrete experience regarding changes in the mental model of educators and education staff that positively impacted the work situation and school progress.			
SP: Pertama tama dan terutama, kita membangun pemahaman cita cita bersama. Cita-cita kita tertuang dalam profil guru, yaitu "menjadi teladan membentuk insan Kolese Santo Yusup yang saleh dan terpelajar", saleh saja tidak cukup, mesti terpelajar/berilmu juga. Sebaliknya, terpelajar dan pintar saja tidak cukup, mesti juga berbudi dan saleh. Cita-cita ini selalu disosialisasikan untuk dipahami oleh semua guru dan karyawan. Setelah memahami selanjutnya disediakan wadah untuk mewujudkannya melalui berbagai kegiatan dan workshop/pelatihan, antara lain penyusunan alur pembelajaran yang menuju keberhasilan profil guru, menyusun evaluasi diri guru, dan	SP: First and foremost, we build an understanding of shared goals. Our ideals are stated in the teacher's profile: "to be a role model in forming people at Santo Yusup College who are pious and educated" Being pious alone is not enough; you must be educated/knowledgeable, too. On the other hand, being educated and smart is not enough; you must also be virtuous and pious. These ideals are always socialized for all teachers and employees to understand. After understanding, a platform is provided to make this happen through various activities and workshops/training, including preparing learning pathways that lead to successful teacher profiles, preparing teacher	Shared goals Teacher profile To be a role model Pious and educated Socialized for all teachers and employee Various activities, including workshop Preparing teacher self-evaluations	Shared vision Mental model Mental model Knowledge Management Practices	Learning Organization KM

<p>menyusun pengembangan keprofesian berkelanjutan. Hingga hasilnya akan diukur dengan rubrik ketercapaian profil guru yang diberi penilaian dari peserta didik dan rekan kerja setiap semester. Anda nanti bisa lihat dan cek melalui RBK (Ruang Belajar Kosayu).</p> <p>RBK muncul karena COVID-19 dan ada informasi bahwa ada tugas yang disampaikan di RBK. RBK sangat penting bagi siswa karena mereka harus mengaksesnya setiap hari untuk bahan pelajaran dan tugas.</p> <p>36. RBK mencakup segala aspek, termasuk keuangan dan administrasi.</p> <p>37. Orang tua siswa mungkin bisa mengakses RBK, tetapi belum pasti. Orang tua dapat mengakses informasi melalui RBK agar tidak kelewatan. Beberapa orang tua memiliki kontak yang sulit dihubungi, namun ada efek positif dari perpindahan ke RBK secara formal.</p> <p>Tambahan pula, secara internal, musyawarah MGLP (Musyawarah Guru Lintas Pelajaran) dilakukan setidaknya satu kali dalam sebulan dan selama ini Kepala Sekolah memang tidak terlalu menuntut</p>	<p>self-evaluations, and preparing continuous professional development. The results will be measured using a teacher profile achievement rubric assessed by students and colleagues every semester. You can later see and check via RBK (Kosayu Study Room).</p> <p>The RBK emerged because of COVID-19, and there is information that tasks are submitted to the RBK. RBK is very important for students because they must access it daily for study materials and assignments.</p> <p>36. RBK covers all aspects, including finance and administration.</p> <p>37. Parents may be able to access the RBK, but it is not certain. Parents can access information through the RBK so they don't miss out. Some parents have difficult contacts, but there are positive effects from moving to RBK formally.</p> <p>Additionally, internally, MGLP (Inter-Subject Teachers' Deliberations) are held at least once a month. So far, the Principal has not been too demanding on documentation, not emphasizing the importance of physical evidence because it can be tricked/engineered. However, based on this</p>	<p>Continuous professional development</p> <p>Students assess the teacher profile achievement rubric.</p>	<p>Personal mastery</p>	
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<p>dokumentasinya, tidak menekankan pentingnya bukti fisik karena bisa diakali/direkayasa. Akan tetapi, berdasar diskusi kali ini, ke depan Kepala Sekolah juga akan memperbaiki tata kelola dokumentasi pengetahuan agar lebih tertib dan bisa dipakai sebagai dasar legacy dan pembelajaran ke masa depan. Menurut beliau, rencana pembelajaran mata pelajaran dilakukan setiap bulan sekali dan harus selalu dikaji ulang. Perlu tenaga khusus dan tidak boleh menyerah dalam pengembangan diri.</p> <p>Komunikasi menjadi faktor penting dalam menyelesaikan kesesuaian permintaan dengan pemberian. Pertemuan informal untuk mengumpulkan informasi kebutuhan. Informasi dapat disampaikan melalui pertemuan kecil secara personal atau rapat formal.</p> <p>Komunikasi informal lebih efektif dalam meningkatkan hubungan antar teman. Pertemuan yang paling akrab adalah saat ada acara atau kegiatan bersama.</p>	<p>discussion, in the future, the Principal will also improve the management of knowledge documentation so that it is more orderly and can be used as a basis for legacy and learning for the future. According to him, subject learning plans are carried out once every month and must always be reviewed. It requires special energy and must not give up on self-development.</p> <p>Communication is important in completing the match between requests and gifts—informal meetings to gather information on needs. Information can be conveyed through small personal meetings or formal meetings. Informal communication is more effective in improving relationships between friends. The most intimate meetings are when there are events or activities together.</p>			
<p>R: Terakhir, tolong dijelaskan bagaimana Bapak menilai budaya pembelajaran/budaya belajar secara</p>	<p>R: Finally, please explain how you assess the overall learning culture in the organization, both students and teachers</p>			

<p>keseluruhan dalam organisasi, baik peserta didik maupun para guru dan tenaga kependidikan? Lalu, Inisiatif atau program apa yang menurut Bapak perlu diterapkan agar dapat meningkatkan lingkungan pembelajaran organisasi dimasa mendatang dalam menghadapi dinamika eksternal?</p>	<p>and education staff. So, what initiatives or programs do you think need to be implemented to improve the organizational learning environment in the future when facing external dynamics?</p>			
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<p>SP: Selama ini, dalam proses kepemimpinan saya bersama para wakil kepala sekolah yang lain, 'Belajar sepanjang hayat' adalah semboyan yang tidak akan luntur oleh waktu. Guru adalah teladan, seperti pepatah Jawa: guru..digugu lan ditiru..Maka guru adalah profesi yang selalu berubah mengikuti perkembangan zaman dan kemajuan teknologi serta kebutuhan peserta didik yang juga senantiasa berubah. Sangat diperlukan membangun komunitas dan mau membuka diri, selalu terbuka untuk belajar dari pihak eksternal dan juga menerima pihak yang akan belajar. Cara pandang dan sikap mental ini adalah dasar utama yang menurut saya mesti selalu dikedepankan siapapun nanti yang menjadi kepala sekolah demi kemajuan berkelanjutan dan terus berkembang sekolah ini.</p> <p>Sekolah memiliki visi dan misi untuk menjadi komunitas belajar unggul berpedoman pada standar nasional dan membangun kawula muda menjadi insan yang saleh dan terpelajar, dalam hal ini ditekankan oleh Kepala Sekolah bahwa teladan dari kepala sekolah dan guru sangat penting dalam</p>	<p>SP: So far, in my leadership process and other vice principals, 'Lifelong learning' is a motto that will not fade with time. Teachers are role models. As the Javanese saying goes, teachers...are admired and imitated...So, teaching is a profession that is always changing, following the times and advances in technology, and the needs of students are also changing. It is necessary to build a community, be willing to open yourself up, always be open to learning from external parties, and accept those who want to know. This perspective and mental attitude is the main basis that, in my opinion, must always be put forward by anyone who becomes a school principal for sustainable progress and continued development of this school.</p> <p>The school has a vision and mission to become a superior learning community guided by national standards and to develop young people into pious and educated people. In this case, the Principal emphasized that the principal's and teachers' examples are very important in shaping students into righteous people. They must be educated in the sense that education must combine knowledge and</p>	<p>Lifelong learning</p> <p>Teachers are role models.</p> <p>Open yourself up</p> <p>Vision and mission</p> <p>Pious people and educated</p>	<p>Mental Model</p> <p>Personal Mastery</p> <p>Shared Vision</p>	<p>Learning Organization</p>
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<p>membentuk siswa menjadi insan yang saleh dan terpelajar, dalam artian bahwa pendidikan harus menggabungkan pengetahuan dan tata krama yang santun, serta mendukung untuk menggelorakan interaksi saling menumpang antar berbagai pemangku kepentingan termasuk orangtua/wali murid.</p> <p>Ada penekanan pada inovasi dan komitmen untuk maju dan belajar. Materi pembelajaran perlu ditingkatkan dengan adanya inovasi dan kreativitas. Inovasi dalam pengembangan sekolah didasari oleh pemahaman akan pentingnya kemajuan sekolah. Inovasi perlu dilakukan untuk melibatkan orang tua atau wali dalam proyek.</p> <p>Selain itu, tenaga kependidikan/karyawan juga berkontribusi. Karyawan harus selektif dan memberikan layanan yang sesuai dengan kebutuhan orang tua dan murid. Ada kegiatan penilaian kinerja untuk perpustakaan dan karyawannya setiap akhir tahun. Ada alokasi waktu dan pelatihan untuk peningkatan kompetensi karyawan. Pengakuan dari masyarakat dan instansi lain merupakan dampak dari upaya yang dilakukan.</p>	<p>polite manners, as well as support the promotion of mutually supportive interactions between various stakeholders, including parents/guardians of students.</p> <p>There is an emphasis on innovation and a commitment to progress and learning. Learning materials need to be improved with innovation and creativity. Innovation in school development is based on understanding the importance of school progress. Innovations need to be made to involve parents or guardians in the project.</p> <p>Apart from that, educational staff/employees also contribute. Employees must be selective and provide services that suit the needs of parents and students. There is a performance appraisal activity for the library and its employees at the end of each year. Time allocation and training are needed to increase employee competency. Recognition from the community and other agencies is the impact of the efforts.</p> <p>Thank you, and stay motivated</p>	<p>Emphasis on innovation and creativity</p> <p>Commitment to progress</p> <p>Performance appraisal</p> <p>Training to increase competency</p>	<p>Personal Mastery</p>	
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Terima kasih dan tetap bersemangat				

APPENDIX D

OUTPUTS OF QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

			Correlations														
			Var1	Var2	Var3	Var4	Var5	Vir1	Vir2	Vir3	Vir4	Vir5	Vir1	Vir2	Vir3	Vir4	Vir5
Spearman's rho	Var1	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.213	.213	.174	.126	.179	-.016	.237	.079	.322**	.119	.039	.148	.250*	.078
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.079	.079	.152	.303	.142	.899	.050	.519	.007	.332	.752	.225	.038	.528
		N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
	Var2	Correlation Coefficient	.213	1.000	.122	.243*	.349**	.357**	.060	.214	.238*	.307*	.118	.158	.221	.347**	.237*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.079	.	.318	.044	.003	.003	.621	.077	.048	.010	.341	.194	.088	.004	.050
		N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69
	Var3	Correlation Coefficient	.213	.122	1.000	.327**	.444**	.284*	.229	.452**	.195	.430**	.335**	.331**	.383**	.385**	.175
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.079	.318	.	.006	.000	.029	.058	.000	.108	.000	.005	.006	.001	.001	
		N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	
	Var4	Correlation Coefficient	.174	.243*	.327**	1.000	.601**	.418**	.489**	.422**	.398**	.348**	.385**	.063	.250*	.486**	.456**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.152	.044	.006	.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.001	.004	.001	.604	.038	.000	
		N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	
	Var5	Correlation Coefficient	.126	.349**	.444**	.601**	1.000	.464**	.308*	.443**	.353**	.411**	.412**	.221	.224	.539**	.402**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.303	.003	.000	.000	.	.000	.011	.000	.003	.000	.000	.088	.065	.000	
		N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	
	Vir1	Correlation Coefficient	.179	.357**	.284*	.418**	.464**	1.000	.338**	.410**	.317**	.388**	.340**	.320**	.290*	.415**	.482**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.142	.003	.029	.000	.000	.	.005	.000	.008	.002	.004	.007	.015	.000	
		N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	
	Vir2	Correlation Coefficient	-.016	.060	.229	.489**	.308*	.338**	1.000	.403**	.309**	.335**	.397**	.133	.341**	.480**	.281*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.899	.621	.058	.000	.011	.005	.	.001	.010	.005	.001	.276	.004	.000	
N		69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir3	Correlation Coefficient	.237	.214	.452**	.422**	.443**	.410**	.403**	1.000	.448**	.532**	.361**	.132	.467**	.314**	.351**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.050	.077	.000	.000	.000	.000	.001	.	.000	.000	.002	.279	.000	.009		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir4	Correlation Coefficient	.079	.238*	.195	.398**	.353**	.317**	.309**	.448**	1.000	.310**	.588**	.323**	.172	.343**	.537**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.519	.048	.108	.001	.003	.008	.010	.000	.	.010	.000	.007	.157	.004		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir5	Correlation Coefficient	.322**	.307**	.430**	.348**	.411**	.388**	.335**	.532**	.310**	1.000	.489**	.356**	.847**	.485**	.337**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	.010	.000	.004	.000	.002	.005	.000	.010	.	.000	.003	.000	.000		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir1	Correlation Coefficient	.119	.116	.335**	.385**	.412**	.340**	.397**	.381**	.588**	.489**	1.000	.488**	.247*	.401**	.440**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.332	.341	.005	.001	.000	.004	.001	.002	.000	.000	.	.000	.041	.001		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir2	Correlation Coefficient	.039	.158	.331**	.063	.221	.320**	.133	.132	.323**	.356**	.488**	1.000	.315**	.322**	.396**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.752	.194	.006	.604	.088	.007	.276	.279	.007	.003	.000	.	.008	.007		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir3	Correlation Coefficient	.148	.221	.383**	.250*	.224	.290*	.341**	.487**	.172	.847**	.247*	.315**	1.000	.524**	.257*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.225	.088	.001	.038	.065	.015	.004	.000	.157	.000	.041	.008	.	.000		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir4	Correlation Coefficient	.250*	.347**	.385**	.486**	.539**	.415**	.480**	.314**	.343**	.485**	.401**	.322**	.524**	1.000	.432**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.038	.004	.001	.000	.000	.000	.000	.009	.004	.000	.001	.007	.000	.		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		
Vir5	Correlation Coefficient	.078	.237*	.175	.456**	.402**	.482**	.281*	.351**	.537**	.337**	.440**	.396**	.257*	.432**	1.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.528	.050	.151	.000	.001	.000	.019	.003	.000	.005	.000	.001	.033	.000		
	N	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

APPENDIX E
PHOTOS of St. Josef Senior High School

Learning Project of Pelajar Pancasila
One of the results of the Pelajar Pancasila project

Documentations of Learning Processes

Moment of Parents gathering 2023

Students Activity in Learning (collaboration)

Students are waiting for administration services.

